

Technical summaries of workshops

Deliverable 9.1

**Funded by
the European Union**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101060836.

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PROJECT INFORMATION

GRANT AGREEMENT NUMBER	101060836
PROJECT FULL TITLE	UNTWIST: Policy recommendations to regain "losers of feminism" as mainstream voters
PROJECT ACRONYM	UNTWIST
FUNDING SCHEME	Research and Innovation Action
START DATE OF THE PROJECT	01 Feb 2023
DURATION	36 months
CALL IDENTIFIER	HORIZON-CL2-2021-DEMOCRACY-01
PROJECT WEBSITE	https://www.upo.es/investiga/UNTWIST

DELIVERABLE INFORMATION

DELIVERABLE N°	9.1
DELIVERABLE TITLE	Technical summary of the workshops
WP NO.	9
WP LEADER	ECSA (Romane Blassel, Leonardo Veronesi)
NATURE	REPORT
DISSEMINATION LEVEL	PU
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DUE DATE	31 August 2025
DELIVERY DATE	30 October 2025

MODIFICATION CONTROL

Version	Date	Authors	Commenters	Changes
V.01	01/09/2025	Romane Blassel (ECSA), Leonardo Veronesi (ECSA)	Mariana Sendra Gallardo (UDEUSTO), Daniel Romero Portillo (UPO), Antonia Ruiz (UPO), Katalin Tardos (CSS), Daniela Braun (USAAR), Luna Kaminski (USAAR), Giuseppe Carteny (USAAR), Rosalind Shorrocks (UNIMAN), Ann-Kathrin Rothermel (UBERN), Mara Businger (UBERN), Colm Flaherty (RUC)	Additions for the Spanish, Hungarian, German, UK, Swiss and Danish workshops, discussion on the conclusion, minor typos.
V.02	15/10/2025	Romane Blassel (ECSA), Leonardo Veronesi (ECSA)	Antonia Ruiz (UPO), Leandra Bias (UBERN)	Addition of ethical clearance for each country, minor edits.
V.03	28/10/2025	Romane Blassel (ECSA), Leonardo Veronesi (ECSA)		

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List of Abbreviations

CH: Switzerland

ES: Spain

DE: Germany

FG: Focus Group

DK: Denmark

GDPR: General Data Protection Regulation

HU: Hungary

RWPP: Right Wing Populist Party

UK: United Kingdom

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Executive summary

This deliverable reports on the design, implementation, and preliminary findings of participatory workshops carried out under Work Package 9 of the EU-funded UNTWIST project. The project seeks to disentangle Right-Wing Populist Parties' discourses and to provide evidence-based policy recommendations addressing citizens' concerns while reaffirming gender equality as a core European value.

The workshops were grounded in principles of citizen science and participatory social science research, aiming to co-develop policy insights with citizens rather than for them. Conducted across six partner countries in May-June 2025, the twelve workshops engaged 101 participants of diverse age, gender, socioeconomic background, and political preference. Recruitment combined professional agencies and local outreach to ensure both representativeness and genuine engagement. Sessions followed a common four-part structure (introduction, problem identification, solution generation, and wrap-up) and were adapted to national contexts.

Preliminary results indicate that participants prioritised material issues, notably the decline of healthcare systems and challenges in the labour market, over cultural or identity-based concerns. While gender roles and representation were raised in certain contexts, they did not emerge as central themes. State intervention such as increased regulation and welfare provision or legislative change was consistently identified as the most credible solution across countries, even among participants sympathetic to right-wing populist parties.

The workshops were well received, marked by constructive dialogue despite participants' political diversity. The method proved effective in fostering insightful discussions, though future iterations would benefit from extended duration to allow more in-depth deliberation. The findings reinforce previous project results highlighting citizens' emphasis on material concerns over cultural issues, and their expectation of state responsibility. These insights will inform the forthcoming policy recommendations to be developed in Deliverables 9.2 and 11.7.

1. Introduction

This deliverable is part of the EU-funded UNTWIST project, which aims to disentangle Right Wing Populist Parties'¹ (RWPPs) discourses and provide policy recommendations to answer citizens' needs, demands and worries related to gender and sex while promoting gender equality as a core value of the EU. This document presents a technical overview of the workshops carried out in the scope of Work Package 9, devoted to co-developing policy recommendations with citizens and stakeholders through public engagement.

The methodology is grounded in citizen science, an "umbrella" term (Hecker et al. 2019) that describes a variety of ways in which the public participates in science, from participatory research or participatory action research in the social sciences, to volunteer monitoring and crowd-sourced science in the natural sciences. While there are many different definitions for what citizen science is, a common ground is a form of research collaboration that involves members of the public in science around real-world problems. The main characteristics of citizen sciences are that lay-people are actively involved in research, in partnership or collaboration with scientists or professionals, towards a genuine outcome, such as new scientific knowledge, conservation action or policy change (ECSA, 2015).

From a historical perspective, the term Citizen Science was coined in the field of natural sciences in the last century. As "scientists" were becoming a paid profession, the need came for a word to describe "hobby" or "volunteer" scientists (bird watchers etc.), who did not necessarily have a qualification and did not earn money from their research. Later, practitioners coined the term "Citizen Social Science", which can be defined as "co-created research that builds on participatory social sciences approaches or social concerns", and where members of the general public make significant contributions to research thanks to their "unique expertise [coming] from everyday experience" (Senabre Higaldo et al. 2021).

¹ The UNTWIST project uses RWPP as an "umbrella" term to refer to political parties that combine right-wing ideology with populist rhetoric. This combination usually includes several of the following components in different amounts in different countries: Populism (claim to represent the "common people" against corrupt elites, political establishments, or international institutions) ; Nationalism (emphasis on national identity, sovereignty, and often the advocacy for policies prioritising national citizens over migrants or international cooperation) ; Anti-Immigration Stance (advocacy for stricter immigration controls and framing immigration as a threat to national security, culture, or economic well-being) ; Law and Order Focus (stress on strong policing, tougher laws on crime, and protection against perceived external threats) ; Economic Protectionism (advocacy for protectionist trade policies, opposing free trade agreements, arguing they harm national industries) ; Opposition to Liberalism (criticism of progressive policies, political correctness, left-wing ideologies, or movements such as feminism, LGBTQ+ rights, and environmentalism); Euroscepticism (opposition to a deeper European Union integration and the advocacy for national sovereignty over supranational governance).

The inputs and the goals of Citizen Social Science do not differ much from terms that social science researchers might be more familiar with, such as "action research" or "participatory action research" (Taugiene et al, 2020). The main difference with more traditional approaches is that research is carried out *with* volunteers, not *on* them. Citizens are participants in the project, not objects of the research. This inclusion of the public in research aims to "make science more participatory, inclusive, and accessible to all members of society, and encourages collaborations that benefit both science and society." (Lorenz and Lepenies, 2023).

Those guiding principles shaped the methodology, analysis, and writing of this document. The workshops were designed to encourage participants to propose solutions to the problems they identify with, building on citizens' experience and fostering a bottom-up and co-creative approach that allows them to influence political discourse. The organisation of the workshops themselves would feed policy recommendations on how to include citizens in policy making (See future D9.2).

This document presents the methodology used to build the workshops, before presenting some preliminary findings, highlighting similarities and differences across six countries. More detailed country-specific information can be found in the appendix.

2. Methodology

Coming towards the end of the project, the UNTWIST consortium collectively decided to build on the data gathered thus far in the project, especially the focus group (FG) conducted in 2023 ([Deliverable 2.2](#)), but also the Typology ([Deliverable 1.1.](#)) and the analysis of demand and supply sides of gendered policies and needs ([Deliverable 5.1](#)). The focus groups highlighted areas in which citizens felt "maltreated", "forgotten", or "undermined" by mainstream parties, such as health, family, education, economy, civil rights, security policies, gender norms, material inequality. This corroborates with the analysis of party manifestos ([Deliverable 4.2](#)), which shows how mainstream parties have shifted attention away from welfare and labour issues. While gender-related topics have become more visible in party manifestos, they are often treated symbolically rather than through concrete policy proposals, with RWPPs framing them in a more negative light.

To continue this exploration further, the general concept for the workshops was to experiment with public engagement on citizens' needs and demands by offering a space for citizens to discuss in small groups their views on the issues they are facing and how those issues should be addressed. Participants were not expected to come up with implementable policy recommendations, but rather with themes that are important to them and ideas for improvement. Based on the experience of the focus groups, it was anticipated that the solutions participants will come up with may not be gendered needs, but they most likely will have a gender dimension (e.g. welfare, economics), as focus groups showed men and women are voicing different problems ([UNTWIST briefing 02](#)). While designing the workshop, attention was given to context specific issues by encouraging local teams to adapt the common guidelines to ensure contextual and scientific relevance of the methodology. As for the focus groups, a protocol was provided to support local teams in their clearance request to their ethics committee. All teams received approval from their institution's ethical committee (see annex vii to xiii).

The following sections describe the guidelines proposed by ECSA and how it was implemented locally by partners. We provide an overview of the workshops (table 1), an aggregated (table 2) and a detailed overview (table 3) of the participants' profiles, and of the activities done in the workshops (table 4).

2.1. Description of the workshops

The workshops were organised in May-June 2025 by the respective local team² in the local language to ensure accessibility and effective communication. At least two experienced moderators³ would facilitate each session to ensure an open and inclusive atmosphere. The workshops were mostly facilitated by UNTWIST partners themselves, with the exception of the UK, where workshops were conducted by a third-party company (Deltapoll) as for the focus groups.

Local teams were recommended to conduct at least two workshops. On average, UNTWIST partners conducted two workshops each, but the actual number of workshops carried out varied depending on financial and organizational constraints: while Spain was able to conduct four workshops, Switzerland and Germany could only conduct one workshop. The target number of participants per country was set to 20 participants, allowing for potential

² Responsible partners for the workshops were UPO and DEUSTO in Spain, CSS in Hungary, USAAR in Germany, UBERN in Switzerland, and UMAN in the UK.

³ All UNTWIST partners participated in a 2 hours online facilitation training on March 11th, 2025 where ECSA invited Sticky Dot, an expert in science facilitation and public engagement.

last-minute dropouts, based on prior focus group experiences. If workshops' group size allowed, participants would be split in smaller groups to foster more in-depth discussion. In total, 12 workshops took place across the 6 partner countries, gathering 101 participants.

All partners decided to host the workshops in person (instead of online). Most were housed outside of university buildings: in private facilities located in the city center (hotel conference rooms in the UK, agency venues for this type of events in Spain and Hungary) or public spaces and libraries (Germany, Denmark). The only exception is Switzerland who had to organize within university because of budget constraints, while still choosing a “neutral” building not affiliated with a specific faculty. In this case, hosting the workshop within university might have facilitated participation, as no extra commuting time was required.

The workshops were expected to last around 2 hours. Overall, the duration of the activities was slightly underestimated, and more time would have been needed to go through all the activities. For instance, Spain experienced that running workshops in 2.5 hours was more realistic than in 2 hours. More time-motivated adjustments will be presented in the following section. Denmark extended the timeframe for the workshops to include a break with catering, which impacted positively the dynamic.

Table 1. Overview of the workshops

Country	UNTWIST facilitators	Recruiting agency	Total # of workshops	# of facilitator per group	Total # of attendees	Location
CH	Yes	No	1	2	8	University
UK	No	Yes	2	1	15	Hotel, city center
HU	Yes	Yes	2	2	16	Qualitative research facility, city center
ES	Yes	Yes	4	3	32	Qualitative research facility, city center
DE	Partly	No	1	3	13	Library
DK	Yes	No	2	3	17	Library ; local civil society house

In accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), workshops' participants received an information sheet and signed an informed consent form. Recordings were transcribed and anonymised, erasing names and any other personal detail mentioned during

the workshops that could lead to personal identification or the identification of other persons, places, addresses, etc.⁴

2.2. Participants profiles and recruitment

Participants to the workshops were either recruited through an external recruitment agency (Deltapoll in the UK, TARACEAS in Spain and CLAM Consulting in Hungary), or by the local teams themselves (Denmark, Switzerland, Germany) depending on needs, capacities and budget⁵. While recruiting without an agency makes prior screening of participants more difficult and allows for less representative sampling, it ensures participants are genuinely interested in the activity. Table 2 presents the main demographic characteristics of participants, and Table 3 gives a more detailed breakdown by workshop. The workshop was presented as a discussion on people’s issues and needs in their daily lives in the specific country, avoiding project jargon. In Germany, the workshops were entitled “*How Should Democratic Parties Address the Issue of Gender Equality in the Future?*”.

Table 2. Aggregated Workshop composition overview

Country	Recruiting agency screening	Gender composition	Occupation	Age	Political orientation
CH	No	Mixed	Students	22-27	Mixed (+ conservative)
UK	Yes	Same gender	Mixed	21-79	Mixed
HU	Yes	Mixed	Mixed	30-50	Mixed (50-50)
ES	Yes	Mixed	Mixed	25-65	Mixed (+ conservative)
DE	No	Female only	Mixed	20-75	Mixed (+ green/left)
DK	No	Mixed	Mixed	18-75	Mixed (+ progressive in one of the workshops)

The following criteria were taken into consideration for the recruitment:

- Regarding **gender**, partners were free to choose either mixed-gender groups or same-gender groups, depending on their methodology and findings in the focus groups ([see Deliverable 2.3](#)), and on their scientific needs. The UK opted for same-gender workshops, as the focus groups proved this allowed more open

⁴ Anonymised transcripts will be available on UNTWISTS repository: <https://zenodo.org/communities/untwist-project/>.

⁵ Recruitment costs varied significantly across countries, which made it impossible for some partners to use this option.

discussions. Germany planned on mixed-gender groups, but men registered participants did not show up. The description of the workshop and its location in the Gender Library, could have increased the difficulty in recruiting male participants. Spain, Denmark, Switzerland and Hungary conducted balanced mixed-gender workshops (4 men, 4 women in each workshop). It should be noted that although Hungary invited mixed-gender participants, the random attribution in smaller groups (people sitting next to each other) led to some same-gender subgroups.

- Regarding **socioeconomic status**, teams aimed for mixed groups in terms of education and income. In addition to socioeconomic diversity, Denmark and Hungary also conducted workshops in different locations, one in the capital city and one in a more rural area, to gather more diverse perspectives across workshops.
- In terms of **age**, local teams were invited to target similar age groups as in the focus groups, unless they wanted to target more specific groups. Overall, the age span covers people in their twenties to seventies. Switzerland had significantly younger participants, due to the recruitment method, which also serves as an interesting counterpart.
- All local teams invited participants who were neither politically active nor affiliated with activist groups, as recommended. It was proposed that the workshops would target participants across a wider political spectrum than focus groups, which focused on switcher-voters to the far right, to ensure that policy recommendation would appeal to a wider audience. Proposed political composition was at least one or two participants who sympathize with right-wing populist parties, alongside one switcher voters, one moderate centrists, and potentially other party voters based on local contexts and requirements. This mix of political orientations was implemented by all local teams except the UK, which kept the same target participants as for the focus groups and invited only people who have voted for right-wing populist parties (RWPP) in the past election or would consider doing so in the next election. Overall, workshops in the UK, Switzerland and Spain had a center to right-leaning majority, Hungary had an equal balance with half of the participants who were governmental RWPP supporters and half who supported opposition parties. Germany and Denmark had a slight progressive majority. It must be noted that not being active or affiliated with activist groups does not mean that participants do not have strong political ideas. This is especially reflected in the German workshops, where participants voiced the stronger focus on gender. It may be that the location of the workshops, in the Gender Library, attracted more people interested in discussing this topic.
- It was recommended that participants do not know each other prior to the workshop to reduce the risk of self-censorship. This measure was more difficult to implement

for partners recruiting themselves, as some participants had invited some relatives to join the event (Denmark), or were recruited from the same course (Switzerland).

Table 3. Detailed workshop composition overview

Country	CH	UK		HU		ES				DE	DK	
Group #	1	1	2	1	2	1	2	3	4	1	1	2
Location	Bern, University	Manchester, Hotel conference room	Manchester, Hotel conference room	Miskolc, research facility	Budapest, research facility	Madrid, research facility	Madrid, research facility	Madrid, research facility	Madrid, research facility	Saarbrücken, Women's Gender Library	Esbjerg, public library	Roskilde, local civil society house
Participants #	8	7	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	13	10	7
Gender	4 women, 4 men	Male	Female	4 women, 4 men	4 women, 4 men	4 men, 4 women	Female	5 men, 5 women	5 women, 2 men			
Socioeconomic	Students	Mixed	Mixed	Mixed	Mixed	Mixed	Mixed	Mixed	Mixed	Mixed	Mixed	Mixed
Age	22 – 27 Average: 25	25-71 Average: 49	21-79 Average: 47	30-52 Average: 47	30-50 Average: 46	25-54. Average: 42	36-64. Average: 51	27-42. Average: 34	44-65. Average: 53	20-75 Average: 45	19-71 Average: N/A	25-70 Average: N/A
Politically active	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No
Political orientation	Mixed (more centrist / right leaning, only some left-leaning people)	Switcher voters	Switcher voters	4 government coalition, 4 opposition coalition (last elections)	4 government coalition, 4 opposition coalition (last election)	4 PP (Popular Party), 2 PSOE (Spanish Socialist Worker's Party), 2 VOX (last election)	3 PSOE (Spanish Socialist Worker's Party), 3 PP (Popular Party), 2 VOX (last election)	3 PSOE (Spanish Socialist Worker's Party), 3 PP (Popular Party), 2 VOX (last election)	3 PP (Popular Party), 3 PSOE (Spanish Socialist Worker's Party), 2 VOX (last election)	Mostly green-left-alternative to mainstream (few conservative)	2 right-wing populist (were part of the FG)	2 right-wing/liberal (were part of the follow-up FG)

Interpersonal connection	Mostly no, but some studied the same subject	No	Mostly no, although 2-3 knew each other	Mostly no, although 2 knew each other	Mostly no, although 2 knew each other								
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2.3. Workshop script

A four-part template workshop script was provided to local teams, who made some adaptations to better reflect contextual and scientific needs (see table 4). The workshops were divided into four parts: (1) introduction, (2) problem identification, (3) solution generation, (4) wrap up.

For the **problem identification** part, the workshops draw on the domains identified in the focus groups ([see Deliverable 2.3](#)). Partners were asked to cover the following domains: **Welfare** (inclusiveness, exclusiveness, health, care work unemployment and pensions, education) and **Family** (household/housework, childcare, adults dependents and elder care, marriage and new families). They could select the sub-codes that were most relevant to their local case, and explore additional domains depending on their scientific needs in the local context, including **Economy** (Economic crisis, motivation for paid work, working conditions, family/work balance, employability and competence, legislation/quotas/harassment), **Security** (economy, physical, social) or **Migration** (cultural, economic). From those domains, local teams would select statements or direct quotes from the focus groups, or turn sub-codes into statements⁶, and print them on paper cards to support the discussion. The German workshops did not use direct statements, only gender-issues previously discussed in the focus groups. Translated cards are presented in the appendix.

For the **solution generation** part, the workshops drew on the solutions categories ([see Deliverable 1.1](#) and [Deliverable 2.3](#)), which identify *external* solutions such as resources, legislation, inclusion, activism, systemic or cultural transformation, and *internal* solutions, i.e. individual adaptation strategies. The following prompt was given to local teams as an example: "*What could be done to solve your problems? Would such a thing as [include measure] help with your problem?*". Below are examples of simplification into prompts, but local teams adapted to their local contexts.

- Relief/resources: *Would you want Kindergeld (parents allowance) to be increased? Would you want to receive free professional training?*
- Protection, legislation, administrative regulation, anti-discrimination: *Would a law help with your problem? What would that law look like?*

⁶ Statements were proposed to be either direct quotes, e.g. "*because I'm working full time I cannot properly take care of my family*" or using/creating a persona, e.g. "*Lilly is a 40 years old woman living with her husband and her 2 kids. She works full time as a nurse. Her biggest concern is that she feels she cannot properly take care of her family*".

- Inclusion: *Would you support a fixed proportion (quota) of women in [specific field]. Would you support bi-lingual kindergartens and schools?*
- Participation and Representation: *Would you support the participation of women employees in the design of sexual harassment policies of a company?*
- Alliance, networking between social groups, activism: *Would you support an Ehrenamtszuschuss (volunteering reimbursement) paid for by the state?*
- Gender language/awareness: *Do you see any benefit in using gender-neutral language?*
- Systemic transformation : *Would you support universal wage?*
- Attitudinal/cultural transformation: *Would support anti-harassment training at your workplace?*

The solution categories also identified agents of change, i.e. who should be responsible for improving the situation. The following prompt was given to local teams as an example: “*Would you like a designated person to work on these issues?*” Below are examples of agents of change:

- Civil society: *through joining civil society organizations*
- Political parties: *joining political parties*
- Education: *educating yourself/others*
- Protest: *joining protests.*

Local teams adapted these guidelines locally. In terms of facilitation, partners were encouraged to use analog interactive tools, such as sticky notes and whiteboards. Denmark used colour-coding both for the problem identification and for the solution domains which helped provide more structure to the discussions.

Table 4 presents the detailed script of the workshops, with modifications made by local teams. Local teams were invited to do at least one short break between part 2 and part 3.

Table 4. Workshop script

Step	Duration	Description / steps	Local adaptations
Part Introduction 1.	~15 min	Participants engage in an icebreaker activity to get acquainted with one another. The goal of the workshop and rules for interaction are established to ensure a respectful and collaborative environment, allowing space for participants to ask questions.	Hungary: Concerned that participants might remain passive regarding the elaboration of public policy solutions, participants were assigned in pairs with the person seated next to them throughout the workshop.
Part 2. Problem identification	~45 min	Identify problems participants face and want to address	
	~ 5 min	1. Participants reflect on their present day situation and think about the issues they are facing in their daily lives.	
	~ 10 min	2. To support this reflection, participants are given the time to read through the cards, and invited to select those they identify with.	
	~ 20 min	3. Participants can discuss and modify these statements based on the issues they are facing. They can write their updated statements on blank cards. Participants are invited to explore other topics, but facilitators must ensure they remain in scope of the workshop.	Switzerland: Due to time-constraints, participants were asked to dot-vote on statements they most wanted to discuss and then explain their choices. Discussion was guided to include the topics / statements the participants resonated most with.
	~ 5 min	4. Finally, participants use dot-voting to select four statements they decide to focus on as a group.	Switzerland: Because of time constraints, facilitators did not do a second dot-voting, instead they suggested which statements to carry over to the second part of the workshop based on what was discussed or brought up by the participants. The participants were then asked if they agreed, if there were topics missing, statements that they would swap with others.
3. Solution generation	~60 min	Participants are guided towards avenues to address these issues (e.g. internal solutions, external solutions). Participants are encouraged to consider local or regional level as well as national level. For this stage there are no limitations, everything is possible. Participants can also be invited to draw or write on cards. Possible prompt: <i>“Think about the desired future situation. How would the ideal situation be?”</i> .	Denmark: Mixed the groups between the 2 stages, which positively impacted the general dynamic and helped vary perspectives. UK: Both groups were invited to discuss if any political parties could provide solutions, but only Group 1 (men) were informed by the moderator that they had all expressed support for Reform UK. This information was provided only at the very end of the session and does not appear to have affected the group discussion.

	~5 min	1. Participants can suggest as many different options as they want, individually, on sticky notes	Hungary: decided prior to the workshops to ask each pair to propose two types of solutions: one they would expect from the state ("external solutions") and another that could emerge from individual or grassroots and local initiatives ("internal solutions"). The aim was to actively encourage participants to think about the latter type as well, since, based on the FGs, we expected less willingness to consider that direction. If a pair could also choose to formulate a proposal in one or the other category.
	~45 min	2. The group discusses possible options together. Facilitators bring into the discussion a selection of the solution categories and agents of change. Participants are invited to create together as many solutions as they like, both realistic and unrealistic. It is not necessary that participants find an agreement, they can discuss but should respect each other's opinions. If there is a consensus, participants are encouraged to explore further how this measure would come to shape	Hungary: pairs were not required to reach consensus and could present two separate proposals or more, if they wished.
	~10 min	3. Each participant gets to put a dot vote on the suggestions they find most desirable. Participants are then invited to share their reasoning behind the choices	Switzerland: no vote, instead, a facilitator showed participants the notes taken during the workshop and asked them if there were errors, things missing or any other things they wanted to add. Reasons for the change were (1) the expectation that no clear-cut suggestions would appear and therefore favored gathering a variety of possible solutions. (2) insightful dot-voting would require a more extensive discussion about the reasons for the choice, which would not have been possible within the 2 hours duration of the workshop. Hungary: dot-voting on the policy solutions dropped after the first workshop as it proved to be too time-consuming, and participants showed little willingness to engage with it. As an alternative, time was kept as the end to go through all the proposed solutions together (had been stuck on the boards), look at which solutions appeared most frequently, and collectively everyone agree that these were the most important ones.

4. Wrap up	~10 min	<p>Collect feedback from each participant on their experience of the workshops, and answer potential questions.</p> <p>Participants are asked to fill in a demographic form (anonymous, no name or address required) for profiling. They may choose the pseudonym they want us to refer them to in the transcriptions (in order to identify the profile). The information to be compiled includes gender, age, education level, professional status, social class, household and personal income, ideology and voting recall. They are also asked to give an email contact if they want to be invited to dissemination events about the project.</p>	
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Overall, the methodology proved efficient for the purpose of the workshops. Main adaptations concern shortening or removing some of the dot-voting activities to reduce time and ensure continuous engagement of participants.

In terms of facilitation, facilitators were encouraged to agree on rules of interaction at the beginning of the workshop, stating that participants should be mindful of other participants, do not need to ask for word turns, but should not talk on top of each other. Participants should be encouraged to respectfully voice their opinions even though it differs from other participants, and informed that the goal may not be to reach a consensus, but to give voice to different perspectives.

Facilitators were directed to orient the discussion towards real life experiences and problems and avoid general discourse. The discussion should focus on participants' personal experiences and avoid general abstract ideas. Facilitators should intervene to redirect the group to the main topic if it wanders too far away, and use previous participants' framing and verbatims to refocus or revitalize the discussion. Facilitators were advised to avoid mentioning partisan labels (e.g., "right," "center," "far/extreme"), and instead focus on practical, day-to-day challenges that participants face (e.g. childcare, family life, welfare state, labor market, gender roles, material inequality, violence), as well as not bring "sex", "gender" or "feminism" explicitly into the discussion unless it is mentioned by the group.

We expected some sexist, xenophobic or racist comments, and encouraged facilitators not to rebuke them, not give explicit or implicit approval and let the conversation follow if the attack is not personally directed among participants. Facilitators were warned to pay attention to signs of distress by participants and try to reconduct and reduce the stress if necessary, and intervene to cut any verbal aggression or disrespect between participants before it escalates.

3. Preliminary findings

We report here the preliminary findings emerging from the workshops. More detailed results can be found in the annexes and a finer analysis will follow in D9.2 (coming at the end of the year). First, we will look at the topics that were discussed, and then we present the solutions proposed by the participants to the issues they identified.

It is worth noting that while we expected potential difficulties in the facilitation due to the topics discussed and the heterogeneous political affiliations of the participants, facilitators

stressed that workshops reception by the participants was very positive, characterised by participants having a respectful and inclusive tone, and a cordial atmosphere with participants eager to contribute.

3.1 Discussed topics

As presented in the methodology section, the participants were asked to first identify the topics to be discussed, then vote for the most salient ones and proceed with the discussion. Here we present a focused overview on the topics that were actually discussed, rather than the selected ones, as due to time constraints some of the voted topics were not discussed in detail. More detail can be found in the annex for each country.

Overall, there was a limited focus on gender in the workshops - similar to what happened in the focus groups. The dot-voting was designed to enable participants to focus on what they were most interested in discussing. As a consequence, in several workshops, gender-related issues that did not stand out in the voting were left out of the discussion. The two main issues for participants across countries were the decline of the healthcare system, and issues related to the employment and labor market. The issues with the healthcare system were selected in all countries but Switzerland. This specificity can be partially explained by workshop recruitment: students may be less confronted with healthcare issues than older individuals. Issues related to employment were selected in all countries but Germany. The framing of the workshop and its setting in the gender library may have encouraged German participants to focus more on gender issues.

Following are the discussed topics, presented from more frequently discussed to less frequently discussed. Gendered roles in the family were discussed in the Swiss, German and Danish workshops. In the Swiss and German cases gendered roles were specifically linked to discrepancies between maternity and paternity leave, stressing the importance of shared responsibilities in the care work within the family. The participants in the Danish workshops also discussed inequalities surrounding parental leave and care work, although the importance of shared responsibilities was not highlighted.

In Spain and the UK, flawed political representation and concern over the rise in the cost of living appeared as key issues. With regards to the flawed political representation, facilitators stressed that participants in the UK workshops showed a deep resentment towards political and economic elites, described as greedy and self-serving, disconnected from the realities of ordinary families. This emphasis is probably linked to the composition of the UK workshops where participants were switcher voters now supporting RWPPs. Similarly, in the Spanish

case (where RWPP voters represented one quarter of the participants), participants emphasised that politicians should be constantly monitored and controlled.

Personal physical safety was a topic raised only in Hungary and Germany. While in Hungary it centered on the issue of safety in the public space, in Germany it focused on sexualised violence, which may, again, stem from the framing of the German workshop.

The role of social media in today's society was discussed in Switzerland and the UK, although the theme was addressed in two different ways: the Swiss emphasised the risk posed by widespread misinformation occurring in social medias, whereas in the UK social medias were criticised for the harmful impact they have on children. This difference in perception may echo the difference in age, as Swiss participants were significantly younger.

Among the less frequently selected topics, climate change was discussed only in Denmark; in Spain there was a focus on the late emancipation of youth; the polarisation on the political spectrum was a theme in Switzerland; gender-sensitive language was a topic only in Germany; and in Hungary there were concerns related to the different generations, in the form of living conditions of the elderly, and the opportunities (housing, employment) for younger generations.

Table 5 below provides an overview of the topics discussed during the workshops, divided by macro categories and countries.

Table 5. Overview of the issues discussed in the workshops

Domains	Issues discussed	Country					
		Spain	Switzerland	Hungary	Germany	Denmark	UK
Economy	Inequalities			x			
	Employment/labour market	x	x	x		x	x
	Work-life balance	x					
	Rise in the cost of living	x					x
	Housing crisis	x					
Welfare	Healthcare system decline	x		x	x	x	x
	Lack of mental healthcare	x					
	Social welfare decline			x			
	Education				x		x
Family	Care work		x		x		
	Gendered roles in family		x		x	x	
	Youth struggling	x		x			
	Elderly struggling			x			
	Late emancipation of youth	x					
Cultural/societal questions	Polarisation		x				
	Social media		x				x
	Flawed political representation	x					x
	Eroding social values						x
Security	Safety in public spaces			x	x		
Gender	Sexualised violence				x		
	Gender sensitive language				x		
	Gender identity				x		
	Feminism		x		x		
Other	Climate					x	

3.2 Solutions proposed

Similarly to problems, participants voted on solutions. Here, we only present those which shared the largest agreement among workshops' attendees.

Noticeably, state intervention in various forms - regulation, increase in social welfare expenditure, etc. - was regarded as the main potential solution for most of the raised issues in Spain, Switzerland, Hungary and Germany. More specifically, state intervention was regarded as crucial to better employment conditions, solve the housing crisis and alleviate the issues weighting on the healthcare systems in Spain, Denmark and Hungary. In the Swiss case it was suggested that passing new laws would solve issues in the labour market, education, as well as for misinformation and polarisation issues within the country. As already noted, in Germany participants adopted a clear gender lens to all solutions.

Participants were also prompted to provide potential solutions at the individual level, although these were taken on only in Hungary and Germany. In both contexts, participants suggested that individuals should get self-defence courses in response to safety concerns in public spaces. More detail is provided in the annex.

Table 6. Overview of the solutions

Domains	ES	CH	HU	DE	DK	UK
Economy (Worsening working conditions; Increase in the cost of living; Financial situation and inequalities; work/labour market)	Social agreement between political parties, employers, unions and civil society.		Increase of minimal wage		More workplace communication	Greater economic security
	Review adjustment between prices and wages.		Training support from the state			Affordable, flexible, and aligned to realistic working patterns childcare
	Public aids to rebuild housing in an autonomous way.		Tax reduction			Affordable weekly essentials (e.g. food)
	Reducing taxes for housing		Progressive personal income tax			A two-parent household would not require both parents having to work multiple jobs
	Build more public housing		Stop offering state subsidies for accommodation that encourage childbirth			
	Improving youth employability					
	Greater corporate responsibility for youth employment					

Welfare (Deterioration of public healthcare system; health and research)	Improving work quality: more contracts, staff, investment, etc.		Financial support for the system	Gender-specific medical research and education; More inclusive clinical studies	State should act more	Reliable access to essential public services
	Improving resource management and achieving greater efficiency		Availability of private health insurance funds	Research on accessible gender-inclusive language closing gender Data-Gap	Local institutions as well	Better delivery of public services
	Awareness from educational institutions about bullying and mental health.		Healthy lifestyle		People should be taken more into account by the state when reaching such decisions	
	More budget for (mental) health care					
Family (Family policies; Caregiving)		Creating a common and more inclusive frame/discourse which allows for a variety of family models, frame/regulation as mentioned in the social cohesion section	Increase in childcare allowance	Strengthen paternity leave and caregiving roles for men; 50/50 parental leave policies; more parental leave		

		Parental leave of one year that can be divided among parents however the family wants, to include different family forms and constellations	Family should be able to spend more time together	Recognise and compensate care work		
		Focus on humans instead of costs / economy	State should support sport practice	Simplify childcare access (more daycare spots, fair pay)		
			Reducing digital dependency	Rethink family models (support for non-traditional structures and Adapt family law to recognize diverse parental constellations)		
Political representation	Improve the professionalization of politicians					
	Increase transparency of public processes					
Social cohesion, polarisation, misinformation in social media		Creating a regulation which allows for individuality and flexibility with certain limits against		Improve training for educators on gender sensitivity; Include external gender projects in schools;		Greater sense of community

	polarisation				
	Through consensus democracy		Invest in political/historical gender education		Happier, healthier lives for children, for example through greater regulation of harmful aspects of social media
	Longtime investments/projects		Better collaboration with parents in education		
	Reform of the education system		Raising awareness of the importance of gender equality for men		
	Law to reduce online anonymity		Better recognition of the childcare workers and better pay		
	Penalties for online misbehaviour		Provide public funding/subsidies for inclusive media productions that avoid traditional gender roles		
	Depoliticisation of social media				
	Focus on social connection instead of economic gain by social media platforms				

		Education on media fruition				
		Transformation of the bureaucratic system: centralisation				
		Transformation of the bureaucratic system: centralisation				
Security			Crime prevention and solidarity	Self-defense for women, behavior training for men;		
				Stronger legislation on sexual violence		
				Awareness campaigns & more women's shelters		
				Electronic ankle monitors & restraining orders		
				Mandatory therapy for offenders		
				No statute of limitations for child abuse		
Gender				No ban on gender-inclusive language; Recognise it as cultural		

				expression;		
				Promote role models and quotas		
				Ensure gender-inclusive legal texts		
Other: climate					State should act more	
					Personal waste sorting	
					Climate-friendly shopping	

4. Conclusion

This deliverable presented the participatory workshops' concept, methodology, and preliminary findings. The method proved efficient in fostering discussions on citizens' needs and demands for solutions. Future iterations would need a longer time frame, even multiple sessions, to investigate participants' issues and solutions in more detail. Mostly for organisational reasons, recruitment methods and participants' profiles varied across national contexts. While this variability and the relatively small number of participants in each country may reduce comparability on methodological grounds, the workshops still provided interesting insights, which, when analysed together with other outputs of the project, help us draw interesting conclusions.

Across most of the six countries, healthcare system decline and employment or labour market issues were the most raised topics. While more "cultural" concerns were mentioned in some workshops, they did not stand out as main concerns. Concurring with the focus groups, gender did not stand out as a "cultural" issue, and the focus was on material issues such as employment, healthcare and housing. State interventions such as increased regulation and social welfare expenditure were widely regarded as the main solution to a wide array of issues, despite participants' right-leaning political affiliations. The focus on the welfare state in the workshops complements research suggesting a direct link between policies of austerity deregulating employment protection legislation and increased support for far-right parties (Vlandas & Halikiopoulou, 2016), and supports the hypothesis of expressive voting behaviour in which RWPP voters mostly do so to punish so-called mainstream parties.

This finding highlights a possible misalignment between the type of state intervention favoured by RWPP sympathisers and the actual economic policies of those parties. Indeed, RWPPs across Europe "undermine redistributive state interventions that would reduce economic inequality" (Rathgeb, 2024), and "while the far right might increasingly talk left-wing on socioeconomic issues, it still mostly votes right-wing on them" (Greilinger & Mudde, 2024), rejecting socio-economic measures that would support workers at the European level, such as minimum wages or access to quality traineeships. At the national level, while in office, RWPPs reduce unemployment benefits and social assistance as well as corporate taxes, while introducing flat-rate income tax and specific tax credits for families and pensioners (Rathgeb, 2020). In Hungary for instance, this mainly benefits "large families and those with middle and higher incomes", so that "the financial support for better-off families has increased, poor families have become less protected under the Orbán

government" (Elsässer & Roth, 2025). This preliminary work will be further developed into policy recommendations in future deliverables (D9.2 and 11.7).

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5. Annexes

i. Technical summary Spain

Country	Spain
Total number of workshops	4 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • G1: 20/05/2025 • G2: 20/05/2025 • G3: 21/05/2025 • G4: 21/05/2025
Total number of participants	32
Recruitment	Through recruiting agency (TARACEAS)
Key takeaways (problems identified, solution generated, workshop proceeding)	<p>Challenges:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Housing: Families face difficulties accessing affordable housing and therefore proposals for rent regulation and public housing were developed through policy discussions. - Health care system: Lack of sufficient support for elderly and dependents requires stronger public care services which were outlined during group conversations. - Labour conditions: Precarious employment and lack of recognition demand stable contracts and better work–life balance which were examined in collective debates. - Youth struggling: Limited opportunities and delayed independence necessitate youth employment and housing schemes which were shaped through thorough dialogues. <p>Solutions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Politicians as main responsible agents: Political inaction and symbolic measures call for transparency and participatory governance which led to broad agreements among participants.
Contextual information and how it affects the discussion and the topics arising	When the citizen science workshops took place, Spain was not experiencing any significant socio-political events that could have influenced their development.
Deviations from the plan, if any	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - There was not enough time to complete all the steps outlined in the story board. - The justification of the selected problems was not well differentiated from the selection of the problem itself. - Not all the participants properly understood the

	<p>instructions to identify pros and cons of the proposed solutions.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The deeper discussion of some interesting gender-related issues was left out, as they did not stand out in the voting.
Composition of the group	
Moderation	UNTWIST partners
Number of moderators	3 per group (moderator, assistant, and annotator)
Theoretical composition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No: 6 to 8 participants per group - Gender composition: Mixed /same gender - Socioeconomic diversity: homogeneous/heterogeneous - Age: 23-62 (similar to Focus Groups) - Political activity: not politically active, non-activist - Political orientation: mixed (moderate centrist + RWPP + switchers + ...) - Interpersonal relationships: participants do not know each other.
Empirical composition	<p>G1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 8 participants - Mixed gender composition: 4 men and 4 women - Heterogenous socioeconomic background⁷: 4 working-class and 4 middle-high class. - Age from 25 to 54. Average: 42. - Non politically active. - Mixed political orientation: 4 PP (Popular Party), 2 PSOE (Spanish Socialist Worker's Party), 2 VOX. - Participants do not know each other.
	<p>G2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 8 participants - Mixed gender composition: 4 men and 4 women - Heterogenous socioeconomic background: 4 working-class and 4 middle-high class. - Age from 36 to 64. Average: 51. - Non politically active. - Mixed political orientation: 3 PSOE (Spanish Socialist Worker's Party), 3 PP (Popular Party), 2 VOX. - Participants do not know each other.
	<p>G3</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 8 participants

⁷ For Spain, "Middle-upper class" corresponds to individuals with university education and a minimum personal income or income per adult in the household of €2,500, or personal income above €3,500 without a university education ; Working-class corresponds to individuals without university education, with a personal income below €1,800 and no properties or rental income (except for primary residence and/or a car), including people (unemployed or currently out of work; with last job reference earning below €1,800) or homemakers or caregivers not active in the labor market.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mixed gender composition: 4 men and 4 women - Heterogenous socioeconomic background: 4 working-class and 4 middle-high class. - Age from 27 to 42. Average: 34 - Non politically active. - Mixed political orientation: 3 PSOE (Spanish Socialist Worker's Party), 3 PP (Popular Party), 2 VOX. - Participants do not know each other. <p>G4</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 8 participants - Mixed gender composition: 4 men and 4 women - Heterogeneous socioeconomic background: 4 worker class and 4 middle-high class. - Age from 44 to 65. Average: 53. - Non politically active. - Mixed political orientation: 3 PP (Popular Party), 3 PSOE (Spanish Socialist Worker's Party), 2 VOX. - Participants do not know each other
Issues affecting the development	
<p>Internal dynamics (e.g power dynamics, participants acquainted, etc.)</p>	<p>The internal dynamics of the discussion group were characterised by a calm, respectful, and inclusive tone. From the outset, the co-creation of internal rules—led by facilitators during the introductory stage—played a key role in creating an atmosphere of mutual respect. These collectively agreed rules, which were broadly similar across all groups, included not interrupting others when speaking, showing empathy and respect, maintaining confidentiality, valuing diversity, speaking from personal experience, and using a constructive tone. These shared principles helped ensure that the conversations were generally fluid and well balanced. Participants were actively engaged and showed a proactive and open attitude towards taking part in discussion and debate, contributing to a positive and collaborative group dynamic.</p> <p>Nonetheless, it should be noted that in most of the groups there were some dynamics as a result of the heterogeneity of the composition of the groups that led to a certain structural censorship of some discourses. Specifically, there was self-censorship in one of the groups among participants from lower social class backgrounds, which meant they participated less, and shared fewer personal ideas and examples compared to the other participants. At the same time, within the same group, participants from higher social classes, with greater cultural capital and higher educational levels, gained greater prominence, sometimes dominating the conversation. In contrast, working-class profiles or those with lower cultural capital tended to participate less. Specifically, issues such as internal imbalances within the groups in terms of social class, cultural capital or educational level meant that</p>

	<p>specific profiles in more advantaged social positions took on greater prominence, sometimes monopolising the conversation, as opposed to other working-class profiles or those with less cultural capital, who tended to participate less. However, the facilitators always tried to balance the discourses, smoothly limiting those people who, due to their characteristics, tended to participate more and, inviting and motivating those who did so less.</p> <p>Time was an issue. On the first day, the recruitment company failed to inform participants that the session would last two and a half hours. As a result, the duration of G2 had to be shortened to two hours to align with the conditions under which participants had agreed to take part. This limited the number of issues that could be addressed, reducing them to just one.</p> <p>In contrast, G1 extended to the full 2.5 hours, but the group gradually diminished as participants began leaving after the two-hour mark, with only 3 (or 4) remaining at the end.</p> <p>Overall, time constraints affected the process, as a two-and-a-half-hour session is limiting for this kind of dynamic.</p>
<p>External context (e.g location of the workshop, news/political context)</p>	<p>The venue where the workshops took place was located in a relatively central part of the city and were well communicated. The atmosphere of the venue was welcoming. Inside the establishment, the atmosphere, the organisation and the decoration of the rooms were neutral, with the necessary elements to favour a fluid dialogue and conversation (comfortable furniture, sufficiently large rooms, materials available, water and sweets).</p> <p>When the citizen science workshops took place, Spain was not experiencing any significant socio-political events that could have influenced their development.</p>
<p>Short summary of the findings</p>	
<p>Part I. Problem Identification</p>	<p>G1: Topics identified:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Rental housing - Increase in the cost of living - Future pensions insecurity - Job instability - Work-life balance - Late emancipation of young people. - Lack of public aid for those who really need it. - Lack of work in the primary sector (rural). - Lack of culture of effort - High tax pressure - Flawed political representation - Deterioration of the public health system - Caregiving roles fall mainly on women - Declining birth rate. <p>Selected topics for solution: The most voted topics were:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Flawed political representation 2. Increase in the cost of living

	<p>Since the duration of the focus groups extended beyond the two hours communicated to participants during recruitment, the group gradually decreased in size after the two-hour mark. The final topic was discussed with only half of the participants.</p> <p>Topic that monopolized the discussion: The group showed a high level of agreement regarding their dissatisfaction with the political system performance. The group strongly agreed on the need to improve political representation and public officers, both in educative and ethical terms. They enthusiastically emphasized that politicians should be constantly monitored and controlled.</p> <p>Consensus/dissensus: Participants disagreed on the role of AI and technology as a solution to the labour and political problems they were most concerned about. This disagreement did not detract from the respectful atmosphere of the conversation.</p> <hr/> <p>G2: Topics identified:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Youth: access to housing, working conditions, emancipation/family life - Transformation in the hierarchy of traditional values - Loss of community support regarding women/gender/family issues - Older people: purchasing power - Older people: care - Difficulty in balancing family and work life - Worsening working conditions and limited career prospects - Lack of recognition for personal effort <p>Selected topics for solution: The most voted topics were:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Youth: access to housing, working conditions, emancipation/family life 2. Transformation in the hierarchy of traditional values <p>Due to having to adapt to the 2 hours communicated to participants by the recruitment company, only one topic could be discussed.</p> <p>Topic that monopolized the discussion: The group showed a high level of agreement regarding their dissatisfaction with the housing access opportunities for young people, linking this issue to the precariousness of working conditions and the difficulties in balancing work and family life. The group strongly agreed on the need to improve working conditions to enhance personal and family quality of life and to promote a dignified life for young people. This is also connected to a loss of community support in facing complex situations and to a shift in the traditional value system. Due to the reasons mentioned above, the second topic could not be addressed, which is why the first topic monopolized the conversation.</p> <p>Consensus/dissensus: Despite showing different points of view and different nuances on some issues, there were no major disagreements on any of the topics mentioned. The participants were adding ideas that completed the</p>
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	<p>opinions previously shown by the rest. The topic that generated the most consensus was job insecurity and its consequences on quality of life and access to housing.</p> <p>G3: Topics identified:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Excessive investment in renewable energy - Deterioration of the public healthcare system - Situation of the educational system - Lack of opportunities for young people: employment, low wages, emancipation - Problem of access to housing - Inability to maintain a household even with two salaries - Not enough meritocracy - Difficulty in caring for older people - Difficulty in balancing work and family life <p>Selected topics for solution: The most voted topics were:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Problem of access to housing 2. Deterioration of the public healthcare system 3. Difficulty in balancing work and family life <p>Topic that monopolized the discussion: The group showed a high level of agreement regarding their concern about access to housing, a problem that most shared by giving examples of their personal situations. The group agreed on the deterioration of the healthcare system as one of its main concerns, pointing to the increase in waiting lists, the poor infrastructure of some centres and the poor management of the system. There was also a high degree of consensus on the lack of opportunities for young people, which they translated as the need to improve working conditions, raising salaries and facilitating work-life balance.</p> <p>Consensus/dissensus: There was general agreement on all the issues identified in the group, and none caused dissent among the other participants. The issues that generated the most consensus were those related to housing, health and work-life balance, although wages and working conditions were also mentioned as related issues.</p>
	<p>G4: Topics identified:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Worsening working conditions - Difficulty of the youth to have a decent life - Lack of mental health care - Wage inequality between men and women - Deterioration of the healthcare system - Rivalry between genders - Increase in the cost of living - Work-life balance <p>Selected topics for solution: The most voted topics were:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Worsening working conditions 2. Lack of mental health care <p>Topic that monopolized the discussion: Current working conditions and public mental health care</p> <p>Consensus/dissensus: The group was characterised by a</p>

	<p>high degree of consensus on issues and solutions. However, the judgement on the living, working and educational conditions of the young people generated a certain dissent at some point in the conversation. Some participants showed their concern for the future of young people, especially their families and close people, while others criticised their lack of preparation, their lack of effort culture or the fact that they are used to lower wages.</p>
<p>Part II. Solution Generation</p>	<p>G1</p> <p>1. Flawed political representation</p> <p>Suggestions of solutions and agents of change:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Improve the professionalization of politicians - Performance measurement - Increase transparency of public processes - Implement technology to alert if processes deviate - Increased coordination between administrations at the state level. <p>Most voted items:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Improve the professionalization of politicians - Increase transparency of public processes. <p>2. Increase in the cost of living</p> <p>Suggestions of solutions and agents of chance:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Review adjustment between prices and wages - Public aids to rebuild housing autonomously. - Consensual strategic plans to set the economy future. <p>Most voted items</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Review adjustment between prices and wages. - Public aids to rebuild housing autonomously.
	<p>G2</p> <p>1. Youth: access to housing, working conditions, emancipation/family life</p> <p>Suggestions of solutions and agents of chance</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - State aid: for families and for housing - Greater regulation - Promoting the culture of emancipation - Improving employability - Increasing public housing - Greater corporate responsibility <p>Most voted items</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Improving employability - Greater corporate responsibility <p>2. Transformation in the hierarchy of traditional values: Due to time constraints, it was not possible to discuss the solutions for the second topic</p>
	<p>G3</p> <p>1. Problem of access to housing</p> <p>Suggestions of solutions and agents of chance</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reducing taxes - Build more housing

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Build more public housing - Public benefits - More affordable mortgage conditions - Decentralising work and remote working - Improving transport to balance family and work - Limiting housing as a business and speculation <p>Most voted items</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reducing taxes - Build more public housing <p>2. Deterioration of the public healthcare system</p> <p>Suggestions of solutions and agents of chance</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - More investment in prevention - Improving working conditions - Improving work quality: more contracts, staff, investment, etc. - Developing more and better hospitals and infrastructures - Co-payment systems - Improving user assistance - Improving resource management and achieving greater efficiency - Avoid privatisation of health system - Develop a more centralised national health system - Health education for citizenship - Limiting resources and services <p>Most voted items</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Improving work quality: more contracts, staff, investment, etc. - Improving resource management and achieving greater efficiency <p>3. Difficulty in balancing work and family life: Due to time constraints, it was not possible to discuss the solutions for the third topic</p>
	<p>G4</p> <p>1. Worsening working conditions</p> <p>Suggestions of solutions and agents of chance</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Taking advantage of the experience of the elderly. - Social agreement between political parties, employers, unions and civil society. - Wage equality between classes. General wage increase. - Greater efficiency in the tax and pension system. - Diversify the productive structure. - Facilitate work-life balance <p>Most voted items</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Social agreement between political parties, employers, unions and civil society. <p>2. Lack of mental health care</p> <p>Suggestions of solutions and agents of chance</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Awareness from educational institutions about

	<p>bullying and mental health.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To reduce social polarization. - Health-education coordination (trained personnel, mental health protocols). - More budget for health care <p>Most voted items</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Awareness from educational institutions about bullying and mental health. - More budget for health care
Debriefing	<p>During the debriefings, some topics emerged, such as concerns about squatting, immigration (mostly opinions in favour of more severe regulations) or criticisms towards political elites, emphasizing that decision-makers hardly take citizen's opinions into account. Participants also expressed that it is very beneficial to discuss issues and listen to different points of view.</p>
Additional topics discussed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Political and social polarization - Incorporation of AI in public administration - Immigration - Criticisms towards political elites - Concerns about squatting
Preliminary conclusions	
Main agreements, if any (points that the majority of the participants agreed on, important conclusions, or major discussion points, explicit if none)	<p>Regarding problem identification: In general, all the participants emphasized being worried about the current living conditions and especially the difficulties faced by young people (housing, above all).</p>
	<p>G1: The current living conditions, especially the higher cost of goods, prevent them from having a good quality of life.</p>
	<p>G2: Access to housing, unstable jobs, and difficulties achieving independence and starting a family for young people.</p>
	<p>G3: The problem of access to housing as a cross-cutting issue across all age groups.</p>
	<p>G4: Worsening labour conditions for minorities, especially the young people, the elderly and women.</p>
	<p>To what concerns solutions: In general, most of the participants pointed out to the government and the political agents as the first line of responsibility to provide solutions.</p>
	<p>G1: Improving government efficacy and political representation through more public officer's and politician's job monitoring and control.</p>
	<p>G2: Improving employability and achieving greater corporate responsibility.</p>

	G3: Improving work quality and efficiency through more contracts, staff, investment, etc.), reducing taxes and building more public housing.
	G4: General agreements among all the relevant actors and decision makers to set a fairer social and political order.
Main disagreements, if any (points that the majority of the participants disagreed on, important conclusions, or major discussion points, explicit if none)	G1: Participants did not express any explicit disagreements, nor were there any solutions that generated rejection among them.
	G2: Participants did not express any explicit disagreements, nor were there any solutions that generated rejection among them.
	G3: Participants expressed explicit disagreements regarding measures involving the privatization of public services or the reduction of the availability of certain healthcare services, increased regulation of second-home owners, and state aid, which was understood as a loss of agency and dignity. These measures were strongly rejected by some participants.
	G4: In the problem identification section, disagreements arose in relation to the youth: while some pointed out that young people, despite being very well educated, cannot emancipate themselves from their parents because of obstacles in terms of employment, housing, etc., others suggested that the late emancipation of young people is due to their lack of a culture of effort and commitment.

Spanish statements (translated)

1. *People are exhausted because, in addition to having to work outside the home to support our families, we have to take care of household chores and our children and elderly relatives. We feel that women's emancipation has been a scam.*
2. *We want to take care of our elderly, but we cannot do so under our current living conditions.*
3. *We want to take care of our children, but we cannot do so under our current living conditions.*
4. *It should be possible to support a family on a single salary, in order to facilitate the development of family life.*
5. *Our way of life, customs and traditions, which we have grown up with, are under threat.*
6. *Today's youth find it very difficult to have a decent life.*
7. *Our elders currently find it very difficult to have a decent life.*
8. *There is not enough support for those who really need it.*
9. *Working people are increasingly suffering from job insecurity and worse working conditions.*
10. *This society increasingly fails to recognise people's efforts.*
11. *Quota systems are discriminatory.*

ii. Technical summary Switzerland

Country	Switzerland
Total number of workshops	1 (Date: 09/05/2025)
Total number of participants	8
Recruitment	Among students through university
Key takeaways (problems identified, solution generated, workshop proceeding)	<p>The participants identified misinformation on social media as well as the polarisation and radicalisation on social media and in society as the most pressing issues. They argued that opinions and standpoints are getting increasingly extreme which inhibits conversations or discussions with people with even slightly altering opinions. This inhibits any change because solutions can only be generated out of consensus and compromise. Without having analyzed this in detail as of yet, we consider this to reflect the current debates around affective polarization and a feeling of erosion within liberal democracies. Further analysis is needed</p> <p>The participants perceive education as an important field of change. Education should also include training of critical thinking and discussion culture to stop the polarisation and to enable people recognise misinformation. Additionally, they also think that rules and regulations e.g. on social media and the anonymity online should be implemented. Furthermore, there should be a bigger focus on consensus democracy and long-term visions and investments by parties.</p> <p>Gender was not a topic that came up naturally. Despite the statements provided all (but two) having a strong gender implication, the participants most of the time did not pick up on this (with the exception of the family discussion). When nudged, participants revealed a rather progressive understanding of sexuality as well as an acceptance of women's inclusion in the labour market (in line with the expectation due to their younger age). Nevertheless, they were critical with regards to feminist policies and also voiced gender relations as one topic that was related to the increasing polarisation of society, which they saw as worrying.</p> <p>Overall, there were some parallels with the focus groups in that participants voiced strong grievances with the increasing complexity and polarisation of society, including the rise of populism. Given the centrality of these topics one preliminary result is that these seem to be pivotal to explain far-right leaning sympathies in society. Gender on the other hand in both contexts seems to be understood as one aspect in which these complexities are felt, yet it didn't emerge as central, but only when brought up explicitly.</p>

<p>Contextual information and how it affects the discussion and the topics arising</p>	<p>Because we conducted the workshop with students, the focus was naturally away from family and welfare (although they were still included in the statements). But, as also one of the participants pointed out during the workshop, these issues are not yet as pressing and personally felt for students.</p> <p>Due to the homogeneous age group, which deviated from the ages represented in the focus groups (dominated by middle-aged people), we added an additional research interest on generational changes by including statements that illustrate how things have changed and attitudes towards that change. We asked participants to reflect on these changes, thereby slightly mirroring the structure of the focus groups.</p> <p>The Swiss context is relevant insofar as participants made explicit references to the Swiss political system and additionally, might be implicit in participants views and utterances. As mentioned above, some of the participants did show a strong affiliation with direct democracy as well as a feeling of superiority vis-à-vis other systems. Additionally, there is a higher level of wealth in Switzerland compared to other countries and as well as a higher sense of safety (partially through conservative politics). The conservative politics of Switzerland were specifically referenced in connection to the family. Swiss family policies are particularly traditional compared to other contexts. The participants discussed the conservative family policies as insufficient.</p>
<p>Deviations from the plan, if any</p>	<p>As described above, we did not vote for the solution generation. Additionally, we made some small changes in the problem identification part. Participants were asked to dot-vote on the statements that they wanted to discuss most and then explain their choices. This way, we were able to guide the discussion in a way which included the topics / statements the participants resonated most with. However, we did not do a second dot-voting at the end of the problem identification part as suggested. We made a suggestion as to which statements to carry over to the second part of the workshop based on what was discussed / brought up by the participants. The participants were then asked if they agreed, if there are topics missing, statements that they would swap with others. These deviations were previously discussed as necessary due to the limited time available. There were no additional spontaneous deviations from this plan necessary during the workshop.</p>
<p>Composition of the group</p>	
<p>Moderation</p>	<p>UNTWIST partners</p>
<p>Number of moderators</p>	<p>2</p>

Theoretical composition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No: 8-10 participants - Gender composition: Mixed gender - Socioeconomic diversity: heterogeneous - Age: 18 – 35 (different from focus groups) - Political activity: not politically active, non activist - Political orientation: mixed (more or less equal distribution of moderate centrist + right-leaning + left-leaning attitudes) - Interpersonal relationships: participants do not know each other
Empirical composition	<p>We only recruited students because we did not work with an external recruitment agency. This caused our group to be more homogenous in terms of age and socio-economic status than e.g. the focus groups conducted under WP2. We nevertheless aimed to achieve heterogeneity along other variables, in particular political orientation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No: 8 participants - Gender composition: Mixed gender (4 women, 4 men) - Socioeconomic diversity: partially heterogeneous, all are students ensured variety regarding their monthly incomes (from less than CHF 500 to more than CHF 3000) - Age: 22 – 27 (different from focus groups) - Political activity: not politically active, non activist - Political orientation: mixed (more centrist / right leaning group, only some left-leaning people) - Interpersonal relationships: some participants (who studied the same subject) knew each other but most did not
Issues affecting the development	
Internal dynamics (e.g. power dynamics, participants acquainted, etc.)	<p>Overall, the atmosphere was cordial and participants were eager to contribute to the discussion. There were no long silences or moments where moderators had to encourage engagement. We attribute this to the group being very used to small discussions due to the university/seminar context. There were 4 participants who dominated the discussion, 2 were not as participatory at first but started to participate more as the discussion progressed and 2 only voiced a small number of short statements. While the participants did not interrupt each other, the speaking time was dominated by the men in the group, reflecting a well-known gendered phenomenon in terms of discussion behaviour and power dynamics. In the feedback form that we had the participants fill out at the end of the workshop, apart from one person, everyone stated that they felt comfortable with voicing their opinions and that they felt safe and respected during the workshop. Upon arrival, it turned out that three of the participants were acquainted with each other because they all studied</p>

	<p>the same subject. At the end of the group, participants continued the discussion (except one who left the room early), indicating that all were engaged and eager to discuss the topics, which was also felt during the workshop. Discussions were held in Standard German.</p>
<p>External context (e.g location of the workshop, news/political context)</p>	<p>The workshop was held in a seminar room of the main building of the University of Bern. The main building is not connected to specific faculties / subjects unlike other buildings of the university. With this, we tried to achieve neutral ground in relation to faculties or study subjects / programs so that people would not feel as outsiders simply because of the location itself.</p> <p>The workshop was held on May 9th 2025 after Trump's re-election and shortly after the German Federal Office for the Protection of the Constitution agency classified the AfD as "confirmed right-wing extremist" which, a few days later, was then put on hold. Both of these political events were strongly influenced by and reacted to within the digital sphere. This might have had an influence on how pressing the issue of social media and misinformation was to the participants. The German context and news of the AfD designation was also specifically referenced by one participant at the beginning of the discussion (albeit with not accurate information).</p> <p>The Swiss political system is often considered to be special and a lot of Swiss citizens are proud of the direct democracy. Although Switzerland is small, there is a certain exceptionalism around the political system. This is also why European politics (EU and individual nations, especially the ones close to Switzerland like Germany) are very relevant for Switzerland. While this was not clearly referenced some of this might have influenced the self-positioning of participants as well as the references to other countries especially Germany.</p>
Short summary of the findings	
<p>Part I. Problem Identification</p>	<p>Topics identified:</p> <p>1. Misinformation on social media</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Dangers of social media for young children especially - Echo chambers on social media (through the algorithm) and how they influence opinions / make them more extreme - Politicisation of Social Media - Social media as a source of news and information - Lack of regulation on social media - Lack of critical thinking - Social media creating divisions between women and men ("All men are bad" rhetoric) - Constant stream of topics and emotionalization of topics on social media (as compared to

earlier when people only occupied themselves with these things for maybe one hour a day)

2. Polarisation in society and politics

- Growing divisions in society and tendency to extreme opinions
- Inability to voice certain opinions / views without getting ostracised (also within friend groups) – especially within left circles (more emotional and direct)
- Unwillingness to discuss / no normal discourse even between people who have similar but not quite the same opinions (focus on difference instead of shared aspects)
- Inability to discuss / unwillingness to discuss leads to lack of self-reflection and self questioning because one is not faced with differing opinions to one's own opinions (> only through compromise something can change) Overemotionalisation and self-identification or self-portrayal (more important than the topic itself)

3. Family policies

- Erosion of the family
- Moral panic around the family
- More equality for non-heteronormative families
- Current form of maternity / paternity leave in Switzerland

4. Feminism (upon request by moderators)

- Feminism trying to erase difference between genders and not strengthening the genders

5. Labor market (only mentioned by one participant in passing – no strong reaction by the group)

- Increasing and unrealistic demands of the labour market

4 selected topics for solution

1. Misinformation on Social Media
2. Growing polarisation in society
3. Gender roles in families, specifically parental leave after birth or adoption
4. Increasing demands of labour market / employers (however the group ended up not discussing this in the solution part)

Topic that dominated the discussion

- Polarisation in society and specifically social media and misinformation

Consensus

- Dangers of social media and through the spread of misinformation / no regulations on it especially for young children
- Polarisation in society, social media and politics as something negative which results in inability to have discussions between people with differing opinions

Dissensus

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Erosion of the family: While someone voiced that they feel like that the family is losing its value / is being eroded, others highlighted that there is a bigger variety of family constructs nowadays and that the topic of the erosion of the family is being overemphasised in the media and public discussions. To them, it is not an erosion but just a part of bigger changes and with that, families can decide on how to live more freely and become more diverse. - Feminism: While someone argued that feminism in Switzerland calls for a complete erasure of gender differences which has a negative effect on the individual strengthening of the genders unlike Sweden where this is not the case, someone else said that they think that Sweden is more feminist than Switzerland and thus women are supported more.
<p>Part II. Solution Generation</p> <p>Disclaimer: We used the WP1 framework to categorise the solutions and listed them along the continuum of least intrusive (regulations) to most transformative, which was developed as part of the typology.</p>	<p>Suggestions of solutions and agents of change This is a list of all suggestions voiced by participants with no distinction between suggestions shared by multiple participants or suggestions that only one person brought up.</p> <p>Issue of polarisation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Creating a frame (<u>regulation or law</u>) which allows for individuality and flexibility with certain limits <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - For the participants it was unclear or difficult to determine who is responsible for setting this frame - Through <u>consensus democracy</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Switzerland with its political system would be a place where such a frame would be possible. - Die Mitte (centre party) has to be strengthened / they have to include topics or issues that are overlooked or only dealt with in extreme ways by the other parties. - <u>Longtime investments / projects</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Parties are not brave enough to make longtime plans and are only focussed on their re-election. They should act with long-term visions for the general good and not their own success as a party. - E.g. Investment in infrastructure such as public transport - <u>Reform of the educational system</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Focus on critical thinking, discussion culture and important life learnings - Censuring of political opinions of teachers (at least until students/pupils have acquired critical thinking) - <u>Investment in education</u> - More support and resources for education

and regulating it the same way in all of Switzerland – responsibility of the state.

Issue of misinformation on social media

- Regulations to reduce anonymity online
 - Although parliamentarians are unfamiliar with social media, a regulation should be put in place which can always be adapted and changed
- Legal consequences / penalties for online misbehaviour
- No social media or a depoliticization of social media (only sharing pictures with friends as it was once intended)
- Focus on social connection instead of economic gain by social media platforms
- Education regarding usage of media
 - Children are most susceptible to believe false information because they have no awareness for it.
 - Encouraging discussions
 - Learning about false information and how that might look like online to detect it in real life
 - Generally: promote and train critical thinking
 - State and not parents responsible for this education (schools)
- Transformation of the bureaucratic system: centralisation and partial dissolution of federalism
 - Areas (e.g. education or law enforcement) that should be handled the same in the whole of Switzerland
 - Systematic problem of federalism as it hampers certain areas and uses too many resources
 - However, because of the cultural importance of federalist system, it should not be completely abolished
 - Maybe the system is not at fault but civil servants

Family policies

- The participants suggested creating a regulatory frame which allows for individuality. Here with the example of parental leave: they suggest that a general parental leave (for both parents) of e.g. 12 months within the first 2 years could be put in place. However, there would be no regulations as to how the parental leave is divided between parents – whether they take it together. This way, different family forms and constellations (same sex parents, adoption) are included and people can adapt the system to their needs. But participants also stressed the importance of having a frame which also sets a certain limit within which adaptations can be made.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Focus on humans instead of costs / economy <p>Most voted items</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - We did not do the voting as suggested in the workshop outline. Instead, one of our moderators took notes during the workshop which we then showed to the participants and asked them if there are errors, things missing or any other things they want to add. We decided against the voting process because on the one hand, we did not expect to have clear-cut suggestions that can be voted on and just wanted to gather a variety of possible solutions. On the other hand, we felt like such a voting required a more extensive discussion about why specific solutions were chosen for it to generate insights. This was not possible to do within the two hour workshop.
Debriefing	<p>At the end of the workshop, we allocated ten minutes for the participants to fill out a digital feedback and demographics form. In the demographics part, participants were asked about their age, highest diploma, whether they study and what study, their political orientation (in more detail than in the recruitment survey), their monthly income and sources of income. In the feedback part, participants were asked whether they felt comfortable to share their opinions, if they felt safe during the workshop, how constructive the discussion was for them, how they rate the facilitation and what could be changed about the workshop.</p> <p>All participants received a compensation of CHF 50 for their contribution after the workshop.</p>
Additional topics discussed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Teachers / lecturers voicing their opinions in classes and courses perceived as negative because university and school should be a politically neutral space - Difference of polarisation in rural and urban spaces: Ability to overlook differing views and opinions in rural areas - Right-wing circles as tolerant because they perceive themselves as a minority - Physical jobs and gender – predisposition of men to do physically demanding jobs which women are not equally able to do - Difference Switzerland and Sweden (Nordic countries generally): Sweden as more advanced regarding gender equality – examples of women working in construction jobs and maternity leave
Preliminary conclusions	
Main agreements, if any (points that the majority of the participants	The majority of the participants agree that misinformation on social media is a big issue that especially affects younger people. For them, the lack of critical thinking is

<p>agreed on, important conclusions, or major discussion points, explicit if none</p>	<p>largely responsible for how much people believe false information they see online. Therefore, they feel as if education and training of critical thinking are essential for this. Additionally, they think that the state/parliament should set more regulations or implement laws to control social media.</p> <p>Participants further agreed that misinformation and especially extreme opinions being pushed online lead to a polarisation that reaches beyond social media into society. They argued that this polarisation is also enforced by parties or politicians to further their goals and by the media. There was a strong sense that people are no longer able to have constructive discussions with each other because they do not accept any differing views. The participants also think that education plays a role here; students/pupils should learn how to have discussions with others.</p>
<p>Main disagreements, if any (points that the majority of the participants disagreed on, important conclusions, or major discussion points, explicit if none)</p>	<p>There were no clear disagreements whereby participants stated that they did not agree with what others said. However, the participants did voice differing views on the role of women and on censorship.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Role of women: The participants discussed whether women can do physical jobs and maternity leave after giving birth. While some participants voiced that women cannot do physical labour as well as men, others did not agree and pointed out that in e.g. Sweden there are construction sites with only women which also do the same jobs as men. Regarding maternity leave, some participants felt that women should be able to go back to work after giving birth and that fathers also get the same amount of paternity leave to shift traditional gender roles. However, other participants pointed out the importance of protecting women and the need for (physical and mental) regeneration after giving birth. - Censorship: When discussing social media and its regulation, someone suggested complete censorship, i.e. no more social media. Censorship was also brought up at other points in the discussions. However, the participants did not agree on this. Some voiced their concerns about it and pointed out the problems of censorship.
<p>Important observations/comments</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Overall, the group was more conservative leaning. - Their solution suggestions largely portrayed the state, law or parliament as the agents or arenas of change. Civil society or protest were not mentioned in the discussion. However, because of the participants being accustomed with the Swiss political system, we presume that they also consider the voting population of Switzerland to play a role within a lot of their suggestions. While they named

	<p>the state or parliament as the responsible agent, for most of these processes, a vote by the population would be expected. There is a general understanding in Switzerland that the voting population plays a crucial role within politics / is included in processes which lead to change. Therefore, although civil society or the population is not stated explicitly within the participants' suggestions, they still might also be included in their perception of the state or parliament.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - There was a strong sense of an apolitical centrist space, which reflects the discourse of conservative parties, which has recently shifted the public and media discourse further to the right.
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Swiss statements (translated)

Family: Change of gender roles within families

1. *In the past, everything used to be a bit more straightforward in a family and responsibilities were divided more clearly. My father worked a lot and was a complete patriarch. I rarely saw him. My mother was at home and took care of us and the household, which was also a lot of work. Nowadays, things are different and there is no longer a clear division of responsibilities. Gender roles have been broken down and now everyone has to do everything. It's good that women can work more and fathers have more time for their families, but the healthy balance has been completely lost.*

Family: Erosion of family / the value of family in society

2. *There is less and less unity in Swiss families. My son and his wife both work part-time (of 80%) and are completely exhausted from their jobs. The children are at school all day and in the evening, they have soccer practice, piano lessons, hockey matches and other hobbies. They all live in the same house, but sometimes I feel like they lead completely separate and isolated lives. I find that sad to see. In the past, the family had a higher status in society.*

Work: Women in the labour market - growing demands, short maternity leave

3. *The labour market constantly demands more from everyone; everything must be done faster and better. This is particularly evident among women. After giving birth, they are expected to return to work sooner and, with that, make their contribution to society. Children are being neglected because they don't get the care they need. Women have to take on more and more because they have to look after their young children and work as much as possible at the same time. It's no longer a question of whether you want to stay at home or not. This freedom of choice is increasingly disappearing in our system.*

Work: High expectations and demands in the labour market

4. *Finding a job wasn't easy for me. I did two internships and still had to write dozens of applications before I finally got a permanent position. The expectations are simply too high. You're supposed to be as young as possible, but have at least five years of*

professional experience and have completed all sorts of further training, and so on and so forth. I've been working the same job for more than five years now, but money is still tight sometimes. Especially ever since we had children.

Feminism: Women's protest nowadays is unnecessary and about erasing differences between men and women

- 5. I think it would have been much more appropriate for women to go on strike in the past than it is now. Back then, they really had a reason to resist or to stand up and say, "Not like this!". Women really didn't have equal rights back then. But now that we can actually talk with each other and now that a lot has changed, I don't think it's necessary anymore. So, I think it's a bit much for women to be marching around with their placards and all that. Nowadays, it's often just about completely erasing the differences between us, between men and women.*

Feminism & Populism: Inability to find common ground and have debates / women's right but not women against men

- 6. The parties and society have forgotten how to come to a consensus. It's no longer about having a real discussion, but just about attacking each other and putting others down. We're no longer working together as equals. It's always left against right, women against men. It is important that we as women make ourselves heard so that we do not revert to the way things used to be. But we must not turn against men. We have to tackle this issue together.*

Freedom of youth: Freedoms of youth vs. discipline of older generations

- 7. I have a 16-year-old son and a 13-year-old daughter. They have an incredible amount of freedom compared to when I was young. Back then, there were far fewer opportunities to flourish. It was discipline that got me where I am today. Young people today don't have any discipline, or perhaps it would be more accurate to say that they no longer need it. I learned to persevere and stick with something in order to achieve something. Everyone had to do that, regardless of where they came from or the circumstances they grew up in. Nowadays, order and rules are increasingly declining, which makes it more difficult to find your own way.*

Social media: Young people feeling of belonging to online communities rather than societies / nations

- 8. I have two teenage grandchildren. I'm telling you: Instagram, TikTok, YouTube, etc. are all things I don't understand. For today's youth, these things are part of everyday life. But what is happening there is pure populism, and that is a danger to democracy as a whole. Young people no longer feel Swiss or European; instead, they feel at home on a subchannel, belonging to some community on Instagram. They begin to define themselves in terms of these communities and are no longer part of our society or our nation. As a result, they lose touch of the problems in the real world and no longer participate in politics.*

iii. Technical summary Hungary

Summary per country	Hungary
Total number of workshops	2 (dates: 26-27/05/2025)
Total number of participants	16
Recruitment	Through recruiting agency (CLAM Consulting)
Key takeaways (problems identified, solution generated, workshop proceeding)	<p>Hungarian citizens have a realistic perception of the key social and economic problems in the country. From the 4 topics to be selected in each citizens workshop the first two most frequently selected topics overlapped in the two groups: the insecure financial situation, including social and economic inequalities together with the dysfunctions of the healthcare system were identified as the most pressing problems. Additionally, problems related to the weakening of the social welfare system, generations, children's lifestyle, and lack of public safety were identified.</p> <p>The main difference between the two workshops related to the fact that in the north-eastern country town, Miskolc, public safety represented an important frustration among participants while participants of the Budapest workshop did not mention public safety in any circumstances. Another difference, between the two groups was that gender related issues, and explicitly problems concerning mothers were only mentioned in Miskolc. However, overall gender-based needs and problems did not surface in the discussion, only indirectly in the forms of family policies, and problems related to children's lifestyle.</p> <p>Concerning solutions, workshop participants strongly held the state (and government) responsible for the extent of generalised social and economic problems and for not implementing the right policies regarding the legitimate need of citizens.</p>
Contextual information and how it affects the discussion and the topics arising	<p>Since the 2023 focus groups, Hungary's political landscape has undergone a significant transformation. A turning point came with a complex domestic political crisis in February 2024, which led to the emergence of a new political actor. This figure quickly launched a movement, founded a party, and by the 2024 European Parliament elections had already secured second place behind the governing coalition. The party has since continued to grow in influence.</p> <p>Workshop participants were recruited based on their votes in the most recent general elections (2022), enabling a valid comparison with the focus groups - conducted before the new party existed.</p>
Deviations from the plan, if any	Regarding the workshop methodology, we made a key decision even before the first session began, driven by concerns that participants might remain passive regarding the elaboration of public policy solutions. To address this,

	<p>we asked them to work in randomly assigned pairs - based on how they happened to be seated next to one another. As a result, some pairs were mixed-gender, while others were same-gender. We instructed each pair to develop policy proposals related to the four selected topics. They were not required to reach consensus and could present two separate proposals or more, if they wished.</p> <p>Secondly, we had also decided in advance to ask each pair to propose two types of solutions: one they would expect from the state ("external solutions") and another that could emerge from individual or grassroots and local initiatives ("internal solutions"). The aim was to actively encourage participants to think about the latter type as well, since, based on the focus groups, we expected less willingness to consider that direction. Still, we accepted if a pair could not formulate a proposal in one or the other category.</p> <p>During the first workshop, we made a third methodological adjustment: the voting procedure proved unworkable regarding the policy solutions, as it was not only time-consuming, but the participants showed little willingness to engage with it. The process became more productive when we dropped this quantitative element.</p> <p>At the very end, however, we set aside some time and went through all the proposed solutions together (which we had stuck on the boards). We looked at which solutions appeared most frequently, and everyone agreed that these were the most important ones.</p>
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Country	Miskolc, Hungary
Group No	No. 1
Moderation	UNTWIST partners
Number of moderators	2
Composition of the group	
Theoretical composition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 8 participants per group - Mixed gender composition - Relatively homogeneous socio-economic status (selection criterion: the participants have completed secondary education as their highest qualification) - Age: 30-50 (similar to the focus group focus groups) - Participants are not engaged in politics - Mixed political orientation: voters of the government coalition and the opposition coalition during the last (2022) elections - Participants do not know each other personally.
Empirical composition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 8 participants - 4 women, 4 men

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 7 participants with secondary education, 1 with a university degree - Age: 30 to 52 - Participants are not politicians or activists of political parties/movements - 4 participants voted for the government coalition, 4 voted for the opposition coalition during the last elections - Participants did not know each other personally before the workshop
Issues affecting the development	
Internal dynamics (e.g power dynamics, participants acquainted, etc.)	<p>The overall atmosphere of the workshop was constructive, cooperative, and respectful. Participants generally engaged with each other in a collegial manner. There was one occasion when a participant reacted to another's comment by remarking that it felt slightly 'personal' (ad hominem), and at certain moments, signs of frustration were visible when participants had differing views or were eager to contribute but had to wait for their turn. Nevertheless, it seemed that all participants eventually had the opportunity to express their views.</p> <p>The method of paired discussions (see explanation below, under 'Deviations') stimulated the overall dynamics. It encouraged and ensured interaction among participants while providing structure to the group dynamics.</p>
External context (e.g location of the workshop, news/political context)	<p>The workshop took place in Miskolc, a city in north-eastern Hungary that also served as the rural location for a women's and a men's focus group in 2023. Miskolc and its surrounding area are characterised by the impact of post-socialist transformation: while the city was a major industrial centre during the socialist era, it has faced various economic and infrastructural challenges since the regime change. The region is also notable for having a relatively high concentration of Roma population, which constitutes an important factor in local social tensions and political dynamics.</p> <p>At the time of the workshop (and in the days before it), there were no major domestic or international political news with the potential to influence the course of the discussions.</p>
Short summary of the findings	
Part I. Problem Identification	<p>Topics identified by us for the workshop in the form of personas based on the Focus Groups:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Financial situation, inequalities 2. Healthcare 3. Education 4. Generations 5. Housing and the Family Housing Allowance (CSOK) 6. Public safety 7. Emigration

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 8. Family roles 9. Children's lifestyle 10. Minorities 11. Workplace and motherhood 12. Social welfare services <p>The 4 selected topics for discussion by participants' voting were the following:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Financial situation, inequalities 2. Healthcare 3. Generations 4. Public Safety <p>Topic that monopolized the discussion: The discussion was largely dominated by the first topic: financial situation and inequalities. This appeared to be due more to the time constraints than to the topic's actual relevance: participants were eager to engage with it, and it ended up occupying a relatively large portion of the allotted time.</p> <p>Consensus and dissensus: Choosing the four topics was challenging, hence several alternative topics were considered important during the voting. There was broad consensus regarding the discussion of the identified problems, and participants welcomed each other's proposed solutions. Agreement was especially strong on the first three topics, where most believed that it is the state's responsibility to improve the situation. In contrast, when it came to the final topic (public safety) participants emphasized solutions at the individual level, particularly focusing on self-defence. Instances of disagreement were few and primarily rooted in personal experiences.</p>
Part II. Solution Generation	<p>Suggestions of solutions and agents of chance: Both internal and external solutions were found for all the four problems. However, external solutions (the role and task for the state, more specifically) has been strongly emphasized in three topics. Participants mainly considered the state as the actor responsible for the solution, except in the case of the fourth topic (public safety) where they emphasized individual solutions and small-scale community duties and practices, such as neighbourhood watch. Regarding the state's responsibility, participants emphasized the importance of fair policy-making in the relevant fields (economy, healthcare, social services and housing).</p> <p>Generated solutions for each topics:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Financial situation and inequality: <u>External solutions:</u> increase of minimal wage, progressive tax lanes, tax cuts, training support from the state, salary scale based on qualifications, seniority allowance. <u>Internal solutions:</u> freelancing or informal side-jobs (based on the hidden but widely known practice of the state socialist era), self-development, trainings, and some said there was no internal solution (which we found informative as well).

2. **Healthcare:**

External solutions: transferring money to healthcare, the state should invest more money in public health, employing more healthcare professionals, penalising irrationally long waiting lists; the state should inject the missing HUF 1400 billion into the health sector (a reference to a calculation regarding the budgetary deficit of public healthcare); the right to a free choice of doctor, 0-24 hours use of medical equipment.

Internal solutions: private healthcare, health insurance; exercise a right to a free choice of doctor. It is informative that one group could not come up with any internal solutions while another explicitly stated that 'we cannot do anything' by ourselves.

3. **Generations**

External solutions: Equal taxing for the young and older people (referring to the current personal income tax exemption of workers under 25); equality, the state should support everyone (not only young parents – referring to family support policies incentivising early childbearing). Increase of childcare allowance (for all). The state should not discriminate based on age. Age allowance (for middle-aged and elderly people), increase in childcare allowance and support for divorced mothers and all mothers in general (referring e.g. to the current personal income tax exemptions for mothers of four, and to the planned tax exemption for mothers of three or two children).

Internal solutions: One group emphasized the possibility of a forum, while the three other groups could not formulate any internal solutions (two left the question alone, one group explicitly stated that there is 'nothing' citizens can do in this regard).

4. **Public safety:**

External solutions: Giving more powers to the police, put more patrols on the streets, providing higher salaries to police officers. Firm police actions and stricter legislation. Motivating officers.

Internal solutions: Self-defence and acquiring self-defence practices (this has been stated by two groups), crime prevention and solidarity. Citizens' watch and similar associations.

Most frequently voted items

We found the voting method not applicable regarding the policy solutions (see explanation below, under 'Deviations'). However, we asked participants to openly highlight if they are supporting a proposed solution strongly. Strongly supported solutions were the following:

Financial situation and inequality (1):

External solutions: progressive tax lanes; training support from the state (here it is important to note, that according to the participants, individual or internal solutions are only accessible if the external framework (i.e. the state's active aid) is present.

	<p>After the group discussion, participants added several new solutions to the list. These are:</p> <p>Healthcare (2), <u>external solution</u>: prevention; also healthcare (2), <u>internal solution</u>: inquiring about 'where the money is'.</p> <p>Generations (3) <u>external solution</u>: increase in childcare allowance and support for divorced mothers and all mothers in general.</p> <p>Public safety (4) <u>internal solution</u>: crime prevention and solidarity.</p>
Debriefing	<p>Due to the participants' high level of engagement in the discussion, the workshop ran somewhat longer than planned, leaving only minimal time for the debriefing phase. In terms of its logistical function, we had already informed participants at the beginning of the session that they would be kept updated on the progress of the project and invited to the dissemination event (if they would wish to be involved); this message was briefly repeated at the end.</p> <p>As for the emotional and interpersonal closure, there were no unresolved tensions or difficult moments that required explicit reflection, according to our assessment. Although the discussion remained lively throughout, the participants accepted without difficulty that it was time to conclude.</p>
Additional topics discussed	<p>Women's situation, gender: The issue of women's situation was raised by a few participants, particularly in the context of discussing generational differences. Several participants emphasized the specific challenges that women face; however, not all participants openly related to or acknowledged these concerns.</p>
Preliminary conclusions	
Main agreements	<p>Participants strongly agreed that the state bears primary responsibility for supporting citizens in the relevant areas, except in the case of public safety, where individual solutions were more strongly emphasized. Several participants emphasized that the family support system should be operated on a more universal rather than selective basis. Additionally, there was a suggestion that the focus of support should shift from families to workers. Participants clearly expressed their disapproval of medical waiting lists.</p>
Main disagreements	<p>No significant disagreements emerged. The few differences of opinion were limited to interpretations of how certain policies had operated in the past (during the state socialist era), while other disagreements were largely shaped by individual personal experiences (in healthcare services).</p>
Important observations/ comments	<p>The group evenly included participants who had voted for the governing coalition and others who had supported the opposition in the last election (three years ago). The</p>

	discussion showed virtually no sign of political polarisation or division: all participants expressed frustration and dissatisfaction. Explicit political references were made only against the governing political forces, and no participants voiced strong support for the government's policies.
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Country	Budapest, Hungary
Group No	No. 2
Moderation	UNTWIST partners
Number of moderators	2
Composition of the group	
Theoretical composition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 8 participants per group - Mixed gender composition - Relatively homogeneous socio-economic status - Selection criteria: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - completed secondary education as their highest qualification - Age: 30-50 (similar to focus groups) - Participants are not engaged in politics - Mixed political orientation: voters of the government coalition and the opposition coalition during the last (2022) elections - Participants do not know each other personally.
Empirical composition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 8 participants - 4 women, 4 men - 8 participants with completed secondary education as their highest qualification - Age: 30 to 50 - Participants are not politicians or activists of political parties/movements - 4 participants voted for the government coalition, 4 voted for the opposition coalition during the last elections - Participants did not know each other personally before the workshop
Issues affecting the development	
Internal dynamics (e.g power dynamics, participants acquainted, etc.)	The general atmosphere of the workshop was constructive, cooperative and respectful. Participants interacted intelligently and respected the forms of civilised conversation and expression. All participants were given the opportunity to express their views. We did not experience any "difficult" moments, and dissenting opinions were presented in a civilised manner. Discussing social

	problems in pairs was stimulating, after which they presented their consensus views to the group together.
External context (e.g location of the workshop, news/political context)	The second workshop was implemented in the capital, Budapest. As in the case of the focus groups in 2023, we had two locations: the capital, and the other in a bigger city in North-Eastern Hungary. For the wider social context, see the focus groups technical summaries (. At the time of the workshop (and in the days before it), there were no major domestic or international political news with the potential to influence the course of the discussions.
Short summary of the findings	
Part I. Problem Identification	<p>Topics identified by us for the workshop in the form of personas based on the Focus Groups:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Financial situation, inequalities 2. Healthcare 3. Education 4. Generations 5. Housing and the Family Housing Allowance (CSOK) 6. Public safety 7. Emigration 8. Family roles 9. Children's lifestyle 10. Minorities 11. Workplace and motherhood 12. Social welfare services <p>The 4 selected topics for discussion by participants' voting were the following:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Financial situation, inequalities 2. Healthcare 3. Children's lifestyle 4. Social welfare services <p>Topics that monopolized the discussion: They were keenly interested in all of these topics, but they were more interested in the first two (Financial situation, inequalities; and Healthcare) and the last one (Social welfare services) that are crucial social problems in the country (beyond the global problem of changed lifestyle of our children).</p> <p>Consensus and dissensus: All four topics were agreed on their importance. There was no disagreement at this stage of the discussion.</p>
Part II. Solution Generation	Suggestions of solutions and agents of chance: Both internal and external solutions were found for the four problems. The external solution was mainly a public solution, mainly related to the financial situation, health and social care. The internal solutions were mainly proposed

because of the dysfunctionality of the state, i.e. the burden (responsibility) falls on the individual.

Generated solutions for each topic:

1) **Financial situation and inequality:**

External solution proposals: tax reduction (mainly VAT); progressive personal income tax, stop offering state subsidies for accommodation that encourage childbirth (as they drive up real estate prices), increasing the wages of employees in the public sector, corruption-free public tenders, support for the small and medium size businesses, offering public housing schemes, higher minimum wage, putting into practice the “equal pay for equal work” principle.

Internal solutions: training & self-development, acquiring new qualifications, purchasing unbranded products, searching for a second job, readiness for change: changing jobs or geographical mobility, producing food products individually.

2) **Healthcare:**

External solutions: significantly increased financial support for the healthcare system; availability of private health insurance funds for citizens (instead of the public one), health screening opportunities available for all, increasing the wages of employees in the public healthcare sector, incentives for employers to support private healthcare services for employees, addressing the shortage of doctors.

Internal solutions: healthy lifestyle, more sport activities, healthy food.

3) **Children's lifestyle:**

External solutions: the state should better support sports participation, practical skills-based education for children, healthier food provision in schools.

Internal solutions: reducing digital dependency, family time / being able to spend more time with their children, more programs together with children.

4) **Social welfare system:**

External solutions: increasing social benefits; more elderly care homes, supporting care at home, specific support for carers of dependents with dementia, higher care allowance for carers, better safety net, more power for local municipalities, to develop the social security system,

Internal solutions: self-savings for the future, using private healthcare, living together with multiple generations (though not everybody agreed).

Most frequently voted items:

1) **Financial situation and inequality:**

External solution proposals: tax reduction (mainly VAT); progressive personal income tax, stop offering state subsidies for accommodation that encourage childbirth (as they drive up real estate prices),

	<p><u>Internal solutions</u>: training & self-development, acquiring new qualifications, searching for a second job, readiness for change: changing jobs or geographical mobility.</p> <p>2) Healthcare: <u>External solutions</u>: significantly increased financial support for the system; availability of private health insurance funds for citizens (instead of the public one). <u>Internal solutions</u>: healthy lifestyle.</p> <p>3) Children's lifestyle: <u>External solutions</u>: the state should better support sports participation. <u>Internal solutions</u>: reducing digital dependency, families spending / being able to spend more time with their children.</p> <p>4) Social welfare system: <u>External solutions</u>: increasing social benefits; supporting home care, raising the care allowance's amount. <u>Internal solutions</u>: self-savings for the future</p>
Debriefing	<p>The workshop went smoothly. It was characterized by a civil, motivated discussion mostly based on consensus. Differing political views generally did not manifest. There was strong agreement on the four selected social issues. In seeking solutions, participants primarily emphasized the responsibility of the state, and in the absence of governmental measures, they saw individual solutions (responsibility) as necessary. In the final phase, they jointly selected the most frequently proposed solutions. By the end, the discussion became particularly lively; however, after the closing remarks, participants left very quickly.</p>
Additional topics discussed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Young people do not pay taxes (below 25 years) - Emigration of doctors - Teacher shortage
Preliminary conclusions	
Main agreements	<p>Participants agreed on the importance of the problems chosen and the solutions proposed tended towards consensus. On the financial situation and health care, there was strong agreement on the responsibility and role of the state. In the absence of this, the emphasis on individual responsibility also came to the fore. In the case of children, there was a greater consensus on individual (parental) responsibility.</p>
Main disagreements	<p>The lack of social welfare services is a critical problem, and there were already differing views (but not opposing views) on solutions. Many saw the lack of social welfare services as being solved to some extent by substantial support for home care. Others stressed that this is not a solution and that it is the responsibility of the state.</p>

Important observations/ comments	The group evenly included participants who had voted for the governing coalition and others who had supported the opposition in the last election (three years ago). The discussion showed virtually no sign of political polarisation or division: all participants expressed frustration and dissatisfaction. Only few explicit political references were made against particular governmental policies, however no participant voiced strong support for the government's policies and it could be observed that opposition voters were more frequently taking the role of spokesperson of the pairs.
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Hungarian statements (translated)

Financial Situation, Inequality

1. *Péter has been working as an operator at a multinational company for 10 years. During this time, he feels that his performance has not declined, yet his livelihood and financial security have been shaken in recent years. His salary does not keep pace with inflation and the rapidly rising cost of living. Observing his broader environment, he has concluded that society has split into two poles: the very rich and the very poor, while the middle class is disappearing.*

Healthcare

2. *István, 45, suffers from a chronic illness. He needs MRI scans, but due to long waiting lists, he feels he simply cannot get adequate care. He is considering private healthcare, but fears it will lead to further tests and unexpected expenses he cannot afford. Gabi doesn't understand the point of paying into social insurance (TB) if, in practice, it doesn't ensure access to care. She also sympathizes with healthcare workers who prefer to work abroad, where they are less threatened by burnout, underpayment, and long overtime hours.*

Education

3. *Hanna and László were informed by the school one day that their child had been disrespectful to a teacher. The teacher believed it was their fault. Other parents suggested a well-placed slap would quickly fix the problem. Their children complain that teachers don't teach properly and are irritable. Hanna and László see that teachers are overworked and underpaid. Often, there are no teachers or substitutes, and teachers lack tools for disciplining children. As a result, Hanna has to spend more time helping the child with learning at home. Additionally, the curriculum is overwhelmingly focused on rote memorization.*

Generations

4. *Zoltán, a 45-year-old skilled worker in a Budapest factory, finds it unfair that colleagues under 25 pay no income tax, or that someone who has two or three children can be tax-exempt for life. This can mean that young or large-family employees earn more than he does, despite his over twenty years of service. He also disapproves of young people frequently changing jobs and expecting to earn 600,000 forints. Zoltán feels the gap between generations has widened, and that young people no longer respect their elders.*

Housing

5. *Kata, 32, is a single woman living in a rented apartment. She and her former partner wanted to have children and buy a home, but the relationship ended. Meanwhile, housing prices have risen so much that she cannot afford to buy a home on her own,*

and support schemes (CSOK, baby-expecting loan) are not available to her. She sees that those who cannot or do not want to have children are almost entirely excluded from support. She believes a housing system should help not only families but also singles and childless people obtain proper housing.

Public Safety

6. *Erzsi lives in a small village and constantly worries about her children's safety. Yesterday, her son was chased in the street because of his new sneakers. She suspects the attackers were under the influence of drugs. She never allowed her daughter to go anywhere alone, and now that she's older, she's even more reluctant. She worries about her friend too, constantly hearing her husband yelling at her. She consoles herself thinking the situation is even worse in Western countries.*

Emigration

7. *Teréz, a 50-year-old resident of Budapest, has three adult children who all live abroad. She is deeply distressed because she rarely sees them and knows they have no plans to move back to Hungary. She understands them, as she believes they couldn't afford to buy a home if they stayed. According to Teréz, young people starting their careers must either move in with a partner or live with their parents to afford housing. Rental prices are too high compared to local wages.*

Family Roles

8. *Emese and Tamás are divorced. Emese has been raising their child, Blanka, alone. She divorced Tamás because he was focused solely on work, leaving everything to her. She believes Tamás doesn't spend enough time with their child during visitation. Child support has lost value due to inflation, and she can barely afford essentials for the child, leaving almost nothing for herself. Since the divorce, she feels isolated and unsupported by the state. Tamás feels he did everything for the family—worked and even changed diapers occasionally. He thinks they divorced because Emese wanted to 'self-actualize,' returning to work when Blanka was only 2 years old. Now he can't spend more time with Blanka because he has to work to pay child support.*

Children's Lifestyle

9. *Yesterday, an elderly couple on the train discussed how different life is for today's children compared to their own youth. Because of digital devices, children spend less time outdoors and lack real friendships. On the other hand, they can't succeed in the future without digital skills. Parents spend less time with their children, barely raising them and often spoiling them. The grandparents lamented that they must work even after retirement, so they can't spend enough time with their grandchildren.*

Minorities

10. *Gábor, 41, with a high school diploma, has worked for many years in a rural logistics warehouse. He has two children, and his wife is a primary school teacher. He feels they both work hard but are not getting ahead. He worries about his wife, who teaches a class with many disadvantaged children, including many Roma. Gábor says these children are difficult to teach, their parents are not always cooperative, and teachers bear too much burden alone. He disapproves that those who, in his view, contribute less receive greater state support.*

Workplace and Motherhood

11. *Nóra, 35, mother of a four-year-old girl, couldn't return to her old job after maternity leave and only found a new one by compromising. Her working hours are difficult to reconcile with kindergarten hours. Her partner also works, and organizing family life mostly falls on Nóra. She looked for part-time jobs, but the pay was so low that 'the*

fuel would have cost more.' They would like another child, but she fears losing her job.

Social Welfare Services

12. Zita, 55, a divorced woman living near Miskolc, is caring for her 80-year-old mother at home. She can no longer manage the care alongside her job, so they survive on her caregiver's allowance and her mother's pension. The allowance and other municipal aid are insufficient for their livelihood. Zita sadly recalls when there was support for adult diapers, but even that has ended. She feels society lacks empathy for people like her and hopes the next generation will be more socially sensitive and that those in need will have access to proper services.

iv. Technical summary Germany

Country	Germany
Total number of workshops	1 (Date: 27/05/2025), with 3 groups (took all place in parallel with a joint introduction and debriefing)
Total number of participants	13
Recruitment	Participants recruited via diverse channels including social media, newspaper ads, and network outreach
Key takeaways (problems identified, solution generated, workshop proceeding)	<p>On May 27, 2025, a two-hour gender co-creation workshop was held from 6:00 to 8:00 PM at the FrauenGenderBibliothek Saar, with a total of 13 participants from various age groups and social backgrounds. The aim of the workshop was to develop political recommendations that could serve as guidance for democratic parties in dealing with the issue of gender equality.</p> <p>Following a brief introduction to the project and the workshop's objectives, three small groups worked on key thematic areas such as sexualized violence, gender-sensitive language and care work. Through brainstorming, personal stories, and moderated group phases, major challenges were identified and discussed.</p> <p>Problems identified in all three workshops reflected both structural barriers and personal experiences of gender inequality. Across groups, participants prioritised issues such as:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Persistent gender stereotypes and unequal roles: patriarchal expectations were seen as limiting women (dependency, reduced career progression) and men (restricted emotionality, societal expectations) 2. Work-life-balance/Imbalance: the 40-hour week was described as incompatible with equal family and professional responsibilities, reinforcing traditional divisions 3. Parental leave and childcare: current structures place disproportionate burdens on women, resulting in pension gaps and long-term dependency, fathers often take only minimal leave, lack of accessible and affordable childcare intensifies inequalities 4. Structural labour market inequalities: unequal pay, limited acceptance of fathers taking sick leave or caregiving, lack of flexible working models. 5. Education: schools and kindergartens continue to reproduce stereotypes, insufficient gender-sensitive training for educators. 6. Media and social influences: stereotypical portrayals in media and the rise of conservative trends on social media (e.g., 'tradwives') were perceived as reinforcing inequality.

	<p>7. Economic and systemic barriers: high living costs, stagnant wages, and capitalist structures were seen as root causes of inequality and stress on families</p> <p>Differences between groups included a stronger structural critique (capitalism, systemic reproduction of inequality) in some discussions, while others focused more on personal experiences (e.g., parental leave, academic support for mothers). Generational differences also emerged: older participants highlighted women's 'complacency' in traditional roles, while younger participants pointed to structural constraints and limited options.</p> <p>Participants also expressed frustration at the slow pace of change despite ongoing political debate.</p> <p>A key takeaway on the proceeding of the workshop was the respectful and inspiring exchange between participants. Many found the workshop enriching as it opened up new perspectives beyond their previous experiences. The workshop concluded with the development of political recommendations at both the local and national levels. Solutions generated by participants clustered around systemic and cultural reforms, some examples are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Legal reforms (equal pay, pension security, mandatory shared parental leave). - Childcare expansion (guaranteed places, simplified access). - Educational reforms (gender-sensitive pedagogy in training, more role models).
Contextual information and how it affects the discussion and the topics arising	German overall context: AfD as the radical right party in Germany as strong as never before (with a clear anti-feminist agenda)
Deviations from the plan, if any	It was not possible to recruit via an external agency because this was (with estimated costs of 6,000 euros) too expensive. Therefore, the composition of the group was not representative
Composition of the group	
Moderation	One group UNTWIST partners, the other two no
Number of moderators	3 (one per group)
Theoretical composition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No: 6 to 8 participants per group - Gender composition: Mixed /same gender - Socioeconomic diversity: homogeneous/heterogeneous - Age: similar to Focus Group - Political activity: not politically active, non activist - Political orientation: mixed (moderate centrist + RWPP + switchers + ...) - Interpersonal relationships: participants do not know each other.

Empirical composition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Age range: 20 to 75 years - Political orientation: Mostly green-left-alternative to mainstream (few conservative) - Political activity: none of the participants is politically active - Socioeconomic profile: heterogenous; 2 students, 10 participants with university degree or secondary education, 1 unemployed - Groups randomly assigned for discussions - no interpersonal connection, but 2-3 knew each other
Issues affecting the development	
Internal dynamics (e.g. power dynamics, participants acquainted, etc.)	Some critical questions have been asked on why anonymisation is needed (we should all have the right to tell our opinions), otherwise the feedback was positive.
External context (e.g. location of the workshop, news/political context)	The workshop took place in Saarbrücken's FrauenGenderLibrary (Women's Gender Library). German overall context: AfD (Alternative für Deutschland) as the radical right party in Germany as strong as ever before (with a clear anti-feminist agenda).
Short summary of the findings	
Part I. Problem Identification	<p>Key Discussion Topics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Gender roles</i> - <i>Gender identity</i> - <i>Inclusive language</i> - <i>Parenthood and caregiving</i> - <i>Feminism</i> - <i>Sexualised violence</i>
Part II. Solution Generation	<p>Policy Recommendations from the Workshop</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Language & Representation: No ban on gender-inclusive language; Recognise it as cultural expression; Promote role models and quotas; Ensure gender-inclusive legal texts - Education & Social Awareness: Improve training for educators on gender sensitivity; Include external gender projects in schools; Invest in political/historical gender education; Better collaboration with parents in education; Raising awareness of the importance of gender equality for men; better recognition of the childcare workers and better pay; Provide public funding/subsidies for inclusive media productions that avoid traditional gender roles - Safety & Legal Protection: Self-defense for women, behavior training for men; Stronger legislation on sexual violence; Awareness campaigns & more women's shelters; Electronic

	<p>ankle monitors & restraining orders; Mandatory therapy for offenders, no statute of limitations for child abuse</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Family & Caregiving Support: Strengthen paternity leave and caregiving roles for men; Recognise and compensate care work; 50/50 parental leave policies; Simplify childcare access (more daycare spots, fair pay); Rethink family models (support for non-traditional structures and Adapt family law to recognize diverse parental constellations); more parental leave - Health & Research: Gender-specific medical research and education; More inclusive clinical studies; Research on accessible gender-inclusive language, closing gender Data-Gap
Debriefing	Took place at the end with the three re-united groups immediately after the three separate workshops
Additional topics discussed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Structural support for student parents (e.g. on-campus childcare, flexible attendance policies) - Social Media's influence on gender roles: "Tradwife" trend , Review and regulate algorithmic reinforcement of gender stereotypes - Capitalism's influence on structural inequality - Cultural and religious influences on gender roles in childcare institutions - Gender as a concept that was constructed during the Enlightenment
Preliminary conclusions	
Main agreements, if any (points that the majority of the participants agreed on, important conclusions, or major discussion points, explicit if none)	The group mainly agreed after discussing each of the topics on the selection of the topics and also the policy recommendations
Main disagreements, if any (points that the majority of the participants disagreed on, important conclusions, or major discussion points, explicit if none)	There were no major disagreements – if any then it was the requirement of non-binary perspective (but after discussion this was also resolved)
Important observations/comments	

German Topics (translated)

- Social role models of women and men,
- Gender identity,
- Gender language,
- Education,

- Parenthood,
- Care work,
- Sexualised violence,
- Feminism,
- Emancipation.

v. Technical summary Denmark

Country	Denmark
Total number of workshops	2 (Dates: 02-03/06/2025)
Total number of participants	17
Recruitment	Combination of previous focus group participants, civil society contacts, random recruitment through Facebook groups, as well as personal contacts
Key takeaways (problems identified, solution generated, workshop proceeding)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Challenges/problems: Strong focus on pressures on the healthcare system, labour market challenges, climate/environmental concerns, with some attention to family issues. Education and Identity domains were not selected by participants. - Solutions: Mainly institutional/legislative responsibility and some individual action, with fewer concrete proposals than problem statements. - Process: Workshop format was highly engaging and participants appreciated the opportunity for direct dialogue on challenges and solutions.
Contextual information and how it affects the discussion and the topics arising (pay special attention to your country focus and how this impacts your groups)	<p>The Danish context definitely shaped discussions, in particular regarding the healthcare system and the social welfare model in general. Underlying high trust in institutions, while at the same time disappointment and disillusion.</p> <p>The political spectrum was more nuanced than in the focus groups, regional differences were notable with Roskilde being the more progressive.</p> <p>The political spectrum was more nuanced than in the focus groups, regional differences were notable with Esbjerg being the more conservative.</p>
Deviations from the plan, if any	<p>We extended the timeframe for the workshops to include a break with a light dinner, which worked very well for the social dynamic.</p> <p>We used colour coding for the challenge/solution domains which worked well to structure discussions.</p> <p>Mixing the groups between the two stages helped with the dynamic and to vary perspectives.</p>
Composition of the groups	
Moderation	UNTWIST partners
Number of moderators	3
Theoretical composition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No: 6 to 8 participants per group - Gender composition: Mixed /same gender - Socioeconomic diversity: homogeneous/heterogeneous

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Age: similar to focus groups - Political activity: not politically active, non activist - Political orientation: mixed (moderate centrist + RWPP + switchers + ...) - Interpersonal relationships: participants do not know each other.
Empirical composition	<p>Geographic coverage: Two cities similar in size, chosen for geographical and socio-economic variation. Esbjerg is located on the Danish west coast, Roskilde in mid-Zealand within commuting distance from Copenhagen.</p>
	<p>Esbjerg (2 June 2025), meeting room at local public library</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 10 participants, 5 men/5 women - About 1/3 of participants had university degrees, and many were in public employment. - Age range from 19 to 71 - None of the participants politically active - Two of the participants were part of the focus groups we did in Esbjerg in October 2023; both clearly positioned on right-wing populist spectrum - Two of the participants knew each other (one had invited the other after seeing the post on facebook)
	<p>Roskilde (3 June 2025), 'Byens Hus' local civil society house</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 7 participants, 5 women/2 men - Most participants had university degrees. - Age range from 25 to ca 70 - None of the participants politically active - Two of the participants were part of the follow-up focus groups we did in Copenhagen in January 2025 (on right-wing/liberal political spectrum) - Two of the participants knew each other (one of the previous focus groups participants had invited a male friend)
Issues affecting the development	
<p>Internal dynamics (e.g power dynamics, participants acquainted, etc.)</p>	<p>Overall the group dynamics appeared very positive in both groups.</p> <p>Participants expressed appreciation for the possibility to engage in democratic dialogue with diverse perspectives. The tone and social dynamics were friendly, relaxed and fully corresponding to Danish social dynamics e.g. use of humour, directness, informality.</p> <p>Participation was generally balanced across genders in both workshops. In each group there were several participants who were more active/dominant in the discussions than others. The moderators facilitated discussions to make space for other participants as well.</p> <p>The moderators assigned participants to the breakout/discussion groups, and made sure that the participants were in different groups in the two rounds (i.e.</p>

	<p>identifying challenges/solutions). This seems to have worked very well.</p> <p>In general moderation focused on structure and time management rather than intervening in or directing discussions, following protocol guidelines.</p> <p>In the Roskilde group, there were two participants whose first language wasn't Danish (in addition to two moderators with accents). We made sure to discuss this constructively, and as it turned out there was no language issue with regard to being able to participate throughout the workshop.</p> <p>Some of the participants noted though that they found it difficult to engage in discussion and take notes (on post-its) at the same time.</p>
<p>External context (e.g location of the workshop, news/political context)</p>	<p>Both venues have been chosen as neutral, accessible spaces known for civil society events.</p> <p>The workshops started in the late afternoon, and included a break for a light dinner ('smørrebrød' i.e. open faced sandwiches, a typical Danish dish) to contribute to a positive social dynamic in the group.</p> <p>The workshops took place in early June, a few weeks before the summer holidays and with no major political events affecting the discussions.</p>
<p>Contextual information and how it affects the discussion and the topics arising (pay special attention to your country focus and how this impacts your groups)</p>	<p>The Danish context definitely shaped discussions, in particular regarding the healthcare system and the social welfare model in general. Underlying high trust in institutions, while at the same time disappointment and disillusion.</p> <p>The political spectrum was more nuanced than in the focus groups, regional differences were notable with Roskilde being the more progressive.</p> <p>The political spectrum was more nuanced than in the focus groups, regional differences were notable with Esbjerg being the more conservative.</p>
Short summary of the findings	
<p>Part I. Problem Identification</p>	<p>Topics: We had given the groups six color-coded domains to discuss challenges in form of 'cases' formulated following discussions in the focus groups (Family-red, Climate/environment-green, Labour market-blue, Health-white, Education-yellow, Identity-pink), but participants did not engage equally with all domains.</p> <p>In both workshops, the groups selected four topics for solution: Participants focused primarily on the labour market (blue), health system (white), climate/environment (green), and some family issues (red). Education (yellow) and Identity (pink) domains were largely not selected; the participants did not express a need to discuss any of the related issues even when asked directly.</p> <p>The most centrally discussed topics were the healthcare</p>

	system (particularly in Roskilde, as there was a nurse among the participants) and labour market issues.
Part II. Solution Generation	<p>There was a strong consensus on the challenges/problems, but perhaps not surprisingly there was more difficulty reaching agreement on solutions among the breakout groups. We had made it clear to the participants that consensus wasn't necessarily the aim of the discussion. Overall, participants identified and discussed significantly fewer solution proposals than problem statements.</p> <p>The primary 'agents of change' identified were the Danish Parliament (<i>Folketinget</i>), politicians, local councils (<i>byråd</i>), followed by individual responsibility (e.g. personal waste sorting, climate-friendly shopping, workplace communication).</p> <p>There was limited focus on collectively organised solutions, apart from workplace representation (e.g. shop steward). Some participants expressed a sense of powerlessness (<i>magtesløshed</i>).</p>
Debriefing	Participants provided positive feedback on the workshop format, the moderation, and the setting. Some participants stated that it was more engaging than the traditional focus groups due to the interaction in the group, and the solution-oriented approach.
Additional topics discussed	One of the broader themes that emerged at both workshops was democratic participation, i.e. participants discussed (and questioned) how citizens can actually influence policy beyond voting.
Preliminary conclusions	
Main agreements, if any (points that the majority of the participants agreed on, important conclusions, or major discussion points, explicit if none)	<p>The clearest agreement, in both focus groups, was that the Danish health system is under pressure (particularly hospitals and mobile/home care). This includes the economic and resource constraints the system is facing, but also related labour market dimensions.</p> <p>There was a general consensus that responsibility lies with Danish institutions, and that solutions require action from Parliament and local councils. At the same time, many participants agreed that the political system doesn't adequately consult citizens before major decisions (e.g. the recent pension age changes in DK).</p>
Main disagreements, if any (points that the majority of the participants disagreed on, important conclusions, or major discussion points, explicit if none)	<p>While there was some disagreement in each group, the tone of this was as relatively respectful disagreement rather than conflictual.</p> <p>The participants expressed different viewpoints on topics like climate solutions (in particular in Esbjerg), female leadership and gender quotas, and EU policy.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Individual vs. systemic solutions: Some participants favored personal responsibility approaches while others emphasized systemic change

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Role of citizens: Disagreement about whether citizens should be more active or whether institutional change is sufficient. - Feasibility of solutions: Participants varied in optimism about whether proposed solutions could realistically be implemented
<p>Important observations/comments</p>	<p>Overall, in both workshops a gendered pattern emerged, where female participants were more focused on institutional and systemic critique, e.g. workplace discrimination, democratic concerns. While male participants tended to focus on economic issues in some discussions (e.g. pension age, climate change), and pointed to institutions for solutions.</p> <p>In terms of format, the workshops seemed to enable a much more interactive and dynamic discussion than the focus groups. Not surprising, perhaps, given that they were designed with this in mind, but just to emphasise that the format worked very well in both our workshops.</p> <p>Both workshops corroborated that finding solutions is much more challenging than identifying problems. In any case with regard to identifying solutions that the participants were then also comfortable to share with the larger group on a post-it note.</p> <p>Participants generally seemed to engage with the challenges we had formulated with an open mind, and on a spectrum of empathy. As it turned out, we had formulated one of the challenges (a high dentist bill) with Copenhagen prices in mind, which was received in good humour by the Esbjerg group.</p> <hr/> <p>The Roskilde workshop was, overall, significantly more progressive in focus, challenges, and solutions identified. We assume that this is not only because of the composition of the group, as there were also two previous focus group participants (plus a personal acquaintance of one of them, who was clearly also positioned on the liberal-conservative spectrum). Rather, it might also be a reflection of the general socio-economic and cultural regional variation in DK.</p> <hr/> <p>The Esbjerg workshop, on the contrary, was politically more heterogeneous, with participants commenting on how they had expected to be alone with their views, and expressing surprise that they found others in agreement.</p>

Danish Statements (translated)

Family

1. *Marie is 57 and has two children. They have both moved to Copenhagen and rarely come home. Marie feels alone and wishes that she had more family around.*
2. *Jørgen has two children. He has tried to be an engaged father but has difficulty understanding his children. He doesn't know what he should do.*

3. *Line and Kasper have just had a baby. They have decided to split parental leave equally. Line wishes that she could be home longer while Kasper worries that his paternity leave will affect his standing at his workplace.*

Environment

4. *Mads lives near Viborg. He drives his car to work every day. He can't afford to buy an electric car and worries that the taxes on diesel cars will soon make it impossible for him to drive to work.*
5. *Marianne worries about climate change will impact her grandchildren. She thinks that it is unfair that Denmark spends so much money on climate policies while other countries don't do anything.*

Work

6. *Anja's office is hiring a new boss. The company wants to appoint a woman to increase diversity. Anja is worried about what this will mean for the workplace culture and for the quality of their work.*
7. *Vladimir has recently moved to Denmark. He previously worked as a radiologist but doesn't speak Danish and cannot find a job at a hospital. He is working in elder care, while he takes Danish classes.*

Healthcare

8. *Christian broke two teeth on his way home from a night out. It will cost 40 000 DKK to fix them. He doesn't know where he will find the money.*
9. *Line is a nurse. She has been on sick leave for the last three months. Although she likes helping others, she doesn't think she can go back to work if the work environment at the hospital doesn't improve.*

Education

10. *Stina's son, Lars, is having trouble at school. Stina likes Lars's teacher but doesn't think she has time to help him. She wishes that the school would do more. Stine worries about what will happen with Lars, if he doesn't get help.*
11. *Alexander is 20 and doesn't know what he wants to do with his life. He is considering going to trade school, but most of his friends are going to university. He worries about what his friends will think if he doesn't go to university and what he will miss out on.*

Culture

12. *Lise's granddaughter has recently become a vegetarian. Lise is planning to celebrate Christmas with her son, his wife, and their children but has recently learned that dinner will be vegetarian. Lise loves Christmas but worries that it won't feel like Christmas without roasted pork.*
13. *Hanne is 72 and the president of the local red cross. All the other volunteers are also retired. Hanne wants to resign but can't find anyone willing to take over her duties.*

vi. Technical summary UK

Summary per country	UK
Total number of workshops	2 (Date: 21/05/2025)
Total number of participants	15
Recruitment	Through recruiting and facilitation agency (DeltaPoll)
Key takeaways (problems identified, solution generated, workshop proceeding)	<p>Problems identified in both workshops were very similar to those identified in the focus groups held in 2023. The all-male and all-female group also prioritised similar issues:</p> <p>Men:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Economic insecurity (food banks) 2. Loss of community 3. Public services (NHS) 4. Social media & impact on children <p>Women:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Work/life balance 2. Economic insecurity (food banks) 3. Public services (NHS) 4. Social media & impact on children <p>The women’s group identified work/life balance as the most critical issue, though it is notable that this was framed primarily in terms of household finances: <i>“Nowadays, both parents have to work to earn the income that they need. Very few families can live off one parent’s income.”</i> While the men’s group acknowledged the pressures facing two-parent households, they expressed noticeably less personal investment in this issue. Conversely, although the men’s group identified the loss of community as a broader societal concern, the women’s group did not personally relate to this theme, and it was therefore not prioritised as a key issue.</p> <p>Shared issues that cut across specific ‘problem statements’ in both groups include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Economic insecurity, driven by stagnant wages & rising prices. - Perceived decline in the quality and accessibility of public services, including healthcare, education, and childcare, often described as underfunded, inefficient or overly-bureaucratic. - Concern about eroding social values, particularly a perceived decline in personal responsibility, increased materialism and selfishness. - Deep resentment towards political and economic elites, described as greedy and self-serving, disconnected from the realities of ordinary families. This fuels widespread disillusionment towards mainstream politics.

	<p>Together, these concerns contribute to a broader sense of injustice: that hard-working, ordinary families are bearing the brunt of problems caused by political greed and inefficiency from mainstream parties and institutions, while others who are seen as contributing less, such as immigrants, benefit unfairly from public services.</p> <p>Suggested solutions generated by participants can be synthesised around a core demand for greater economic security and better delivery of public services. An ideal scenario for participants would be a society where a two-parent household would not require both parents having to work multiple jobs; where childcare was affordable, flexible, and aligned to realistic working patterns; where weekly essentials such as food were easily affordable; and where access to essential services, such as GP appointments, was straightforward and reliable. In addition, participants expressed a desire for greater community – both in terms of shared societal values and local provision of services – and happier, healthier lives for children, for example through greater regulation of harmful aspects of social media.</p>
<p>Contextual information and how it affects the discussion and the topics arising (pay special attention to your country focus and how this impacts your groups)</p>	<p>The workshops took place a few weeks after local elections across England in which Reform UK won the majority of council seats/councils, as well as a by-election for a parliamentary seat. This was a substantial blow for the incumbent Labour government, which had faced growing criticism since the general election less than a year previous. This political context framed the discussion in both groups, with participants expressing frustration at the perceived failings of the current government, disappointment at the lack of meaningful change from the previous Conservative government, and a broader sense that the political system required a fundamental ‘shake-up’.</p> <p>Another important factor is the ongoing ‘cost-of-living’ crisis in the UK, which began in 2021, characterised by a significant increase in the price of everyday essentials like food and energy. These price rises have outpaced rises in wages and household incomes, leading to widespread financial hardship. This has become a central issue in public debate and has shaped perceptions of government competence.</p> <p>Discussion was also framed by the high salience of immigration in political and media discourse. Specifically – and particularly for RWPP voters – there are strong concerns about migrants arriving via small boat crossings from France. For both workshops, moderators were instructed to redirect conversations away from immigration in order to maintain focus on areas more directly relevant to the aims of UNTWIST. Nevertheless, the perceived impact of immigration remained a latent concern linked by some participants to issues such as housing, NHS access, and welfare provision.</p>

Deviations from the plan, if any	<p>No specific criteria were set regarding participant ethnicity during recruitment and the resulting groups were both ethnically heterogeneous. This diversity did not appear to hinder discussion in either group.</p> <p>Both groups were invited to discuss if any political parties could provide solutions, but only Group 1 (men) were informed by the moderator that they had all expressed support for Reform UK. This information was provided only at the very end of the session and does not appear to have affected the group discussion.</p>
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Country	UK
Group No	1 (Men only)
Number of moderators	1
Moderation	DeltaPoll
Composition of the group	
Theoretical composition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No: 6 to 8 participants per group - Gender composition: men - Socioeconomic diversity: heterogeneous - Age: Heterogenous - Political activity: non activist - Political orientation: Switcher voters i.e., those who have voted for RWPP in past election or would consider voting RWPP in the next election - Interpersonal relationships: participants do not know each other.
Empirical composition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No: 7 - Gender composition: Male - Socioeconomic diversity: heterogeneous (managers, supervisors, public sector employees, manual workers ; employed, unemployed and retired) - Age: Heterogenous, ranging 25-71 - Political activity: non activist - Political orientation: Switcher voters i.e., those who have voted for RWPP in past election or would consider voting RWPP in the next election - Interpersonal relationships: participants do not know each other. - Ethnicity: heterogenous including white British and British Asian – this was not specified in theoretical composition guidelines but does not appear to have adversely affected discussion.
Issues affecting the development	
Internal dynamics (e.g)	None of the participants were acquainted with each other.

<p>power dynamics, participants acquainted, etc.)</p>	<p>There was a fairly relaxed and respectful dynamic with participants listening and reacting to each other's views and feeling comfortable to disagree with one another. Disagreements were framed as 'alternative points of view' rather than direct contentions.</p> <p>A notable dynamic influencing discussion was age, with older participants often reflecting that their differing views stemmed from coming from an older generation.</p> <p>Additionally, two participants identified their ethnicity as British Asian, however this does not appear to have affected the content or tone of the discussion, for example, several white participants used racialised language when talking about immigration without conflict.</p>
<p>External context (e.g location of the workshop, news/political context)</p>	<p>The workshop was hosted at a hotel in Manchester City Centre. This avoided overtly framing the workshops as part of 'academic research' in comparison to hosting at a University venue.</p> <p>The workshops took place a few weeks after local elections across England in which Reform UK won the majority of council seats/councils, as well as a by-election for a parliamentary seat.</p> <p>Local context also impacted discussion, for example several times participants referenced 'Cresta Court' – a hotel being used to house asylum seekers in Greater Manchester.</p>
<p>Short summary of the findings</p>	
<p>Part I. Problem Identification</p>	<p>Topics identified: Participants were presented with 'problem statements' in the form of quotes taken from the 2023 focus groups, each representing a key challenge that was previously identified. The quotes were shown to the participants on a card and read aloud by the moderator, who occasionally prompted discussion by highlighting the general theme to which each quote related. E.g.,</p> <p>Card 6: Increasing care responsibilities for elderly parents/state of care provision</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o <i>“As soon as our parents get older, we shove them in a home, they've got something wrong with them, I've not got enough time to look after them, they get shoved in a home.”</i> <p>Participants were asked to discuss the problem statements and reflect on whether they agreed/disagreed that these represented problems for the country as a whole. However, participants often reflected on whether their personal situation related to the quote, with moderators steering discussion back to societal level.</p> <p>Findings: Participants' expressed very similar attitudes to those of the 2023 focus group participants. They largely</p>

agreed with the problem statements and identified that same causes/consequences:

1. **Balancing work and family life** – General agreement that it would be better for children if one parent stayed at home (ideally the mother) but that current economic situation and employment practices e.g., inflexible working hours, poor job protection, cost of childcare mean that this isn't feasible. Also, that balancing parenting with full-time work puts pressure on parents, particularly in terms of mental health, and that a factor driving this is increased materialism/erosion of social values.
2. **Loss of community; consumerism/greed** – General agreement that there has been a loss of community and social interaction in comparison to 20/30 years ago. Strong nostalgia about childhood where 'everyone knew each other'. Lack of community blamed on social media and immigration without integration.
3. **Social media & impact on young people** – Very strong reaction against social media and the impact on children's mental health and ability for social interaction.
4. **Economic insecurity & failing public services** – Strong empathy with concerns about the cost-of-living crisis and perception that working people are paying (via taxes) for failing public services.
5. **Increasing care responsibilities for elderly parents/state of care provision** – This was the only topic in which workshop participants collectively pushed back against a problem statement : *"as soon as our parents get older, we shove 'em in a home. They've got something wrong with 'em. I've not got enough time to look after them. They get shoved in at home"*. This was met with general disagreement as participants felt there were nuanced and beneficial reasons for using private/government care.

4 selected topics for solution: Participants ranked each problem statement and the first four were taken through to the next stage. The top four were:

1. Economic insecurity (food banks)
2. Loss of communities
3. Public services (National Health Service (NHS))
4. Social media & impact on children

Topic that monopolized the discussion: Discussion moved swiftly from topic to topic due to time constraints but recurring themes that were connected across topics were immigration – specifically spending on asylum seekers & integration of immigrants – as well as a perceived increase in materialism/erosion of values and disillusionment from

	<p>mainstream parties and anger/distrust with political, economic, and media elites. These were seen as causes & consequences of multiple issues.</p> <p>Consensus/dissensus: There was strong consensus among the group in relation to the ‘problem statements’ from the previous focus groups. Where there was dissensus, it mostly came from differences in participants’ personal experiences e.g., their own family models and impact on their childcare arrangements. The only trend of difference in opinion was across age, with older participants often reflecting that issues that had been identified as ‘new’ phenomena by other participants e.g., materialism, had in fact persisted in their youth.</p>
Part II. Solution Generation	<p>Suggestions of solutions and agents of chance: Participants first discussed what ‘ideal solutions/scenarios’ looked like for each of the top four topics. The aim was to keep the discussion ideational and focus on a ‘dream scenario’, however in practice, moderators found it very difficult to guide participants from thinking about practicalities, problems, and specific policies. After a brief exercise outlining ideal solutions, participants split into small groups and discuss the practical steps they would put in place to reach those outcomes. Participants were again encouraged to think outside of the box and develop creative solutions. Groups joined and fed back their thoughts and discussed agreement/disagreement.</p> <p>Findings: <i>Ideal scenarios (participants found it difficult to talk about goals/end scenarios rather than the steps that need to be taken to address problems.):</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Economic insecurity (foodbanks): There won’t be a need for food banks – food is affordable for all. - Loss of communities: Fully integrated communities - Public services (NHS): Better accessibility – lower waiting times - Social media & impact on children: That it would be a good influence rather than a bad influence. That it should represent positive societal standards. <p>Small group activity:</p> <p>Group 1 – Economic insecurity (food banks):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Better system for distributing surplus food - Increase benefits for most deserving - Improved systems to help unemployed people into education & work e.g., apprenticeships - Reduce childcare (particularly nursery) costs, so there is greater benefit to women working. <p>Group 2 – Loss of communities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increase individual responsibility to resolve local problems e.g., fly-tipping by setting up WhatsApp groups or organising local groups - Community leaders & independent councillors who

	<p style="text-align: center;">motivate people</p> <p>Group 3 – Public services (NHS):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cut travelling costs between hospitals - Have suggestion boxes in local surgeries for improvements to cut costs and increase efficiency - Remove higher paid administrative staff and increase pay for nurses/doctors to remove bureaucracy - Ban cigarettes, alcohol, junk food to remove pressure. Focus on prevention rather than cure <p>Group 4 – Social media & impact on children</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ban monetised posts & adverts as a way to reduce power of influencers. The consequence would be a less toxic atmosphere on social media e.g., rage bait posts & unhealthy beauty standards that have a negative impact on children’s mental health. - Stronger controls on 18+ content to promote healthier attitudes towards sex - Stronger regulations on social media companies <p>Group discussion: The group as a whole largely agreed with all solutions suggested by each small group. When asked to reflect on the likelihood of the solutions, participants were not optimistic that as a society/nation steps are being currently taken to address these problems. When asked if there is anybody who could take steps to deal with these issues, participants collectively felt that the UK needs a stronger society and more power in the hands of ‘the people’, although several participants were not in favour of mass protest without concrete solutions.</p> <p>Most voted items: N/A</p>
Debriefing	N/A
Additional topics discussed	<p>The ‘solution generation’ phase ended with the moderator asking participants if they felt any current political party in the UK would be capable of enacting the solutions they had outlined. There was resounding agreement that political parties were not making any steps toward solutions. In the all-male group, the moderator did inform participants that they had all expressed support for Reform UK and directly asked if Reform/Nigel Farage could provide solutions. Participants didn’t express support for specific policies but felt that Reform UK could more generally provide the ‘shake up’ to the system that they felt was needed.</p>
Preliminary conclusions	
Main agreements, if any (points that the majority of the participants agreed on, important conclusions, or major discussion points,	<p>Agreement predominantly oriented around identifying problems e.g.,</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Disillusionment with mainstream politics and mainstream parties/politicians – need for a ‘shake up’ to the system

<p>explicit if none</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Frustration & anger over immigration and perception of mis-spent resources that should be spent on 'native' citizens. We find evidence of participants misdirecting their frustration with economic insecurity and poor public service provision towards immigrants, and particularly asylum seekers. - Relatedly, a shared concern with the cost of living & economic strain on 'ordinary' people with anger directed towards immigrants and elites. - Perceived decline of community and erosion of local/neighbourhood relationships and trust <p>Agreement over solutions to these problems included:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Eliminating the need for food banks by reducing poverty and improving access to essentials. - Restoring social cohesion and individual responsibility. There was a focus across issues on solutions that lead to improved social order/values without requiring government spending - Similarly, improving public services like the National Health Service (NHS) by cutting bureaucracy and increasing efficiency, without increasing spending - Reduce social media's harmful impact on children and self-esteem through stronger regulation on social media content - Community solutions were preferred over reliance on politicians who are deemed untrustworthy and ineffective.
<p>Main disagreements, if any (points that the majority of the participants disagreed on, important conclusions, or major discussion points, explicit if none)</p>	<p>There were no major points of disagreement on the problems identified. Where participants expressed disagreement, it was often situated within their own personal situations and ability to relate to a problem statement. Otherwise, there was minor disagreement about the realism of some suggested solutions.</p> <p>Points where respondents showed more variety in opinions were:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - That British society was better 20-30 years ago, particularly in terms of social order and values and work/life balance. Here, the older participants reflected that society has not changed as much as people often think. - That mass protest is an effective response to dissatisfaction with the current political/social/economic situation - Interestingly, while all supporting Reform UK, not all participants felt party leader Nigel Farage was any more honest/reputable than other politicians.
<p>Important observations/comments</p>	<p>Moderators found it difficult to encourage participants to develop idealistic or 'unrealistic' solutions to the problems they had identified. Instead, participants developed</p>

	<p>pragmatic solutions, often focused on cost-saving and efficiency within existing systems. When a participant did suggest a more 'radical' solution, it was often met with pragmatics from other participants e.g., one participant suggested a government price cap on food prices, which was immediately labelled as unrealistic by another participant.</p> <p>From the discussion of political parties, we find further evidence that participant's support for RWPPs is predominantly expressive rather than instrumental. When asked whether Reform UK could provide the solutions participants had produced, discussion focused on how the party could 'shake up' the political system, but there was no mention of their actual policies.</p>
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Country	UK
Group No	2 (Women only)
Number of moderators	1
Moderation	DeltaPoll
Composition of the group	
Theoretical composition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No: 6 to 8 participants per group - Gender composition: Same gender - Socioeconomic diversity: Heterogeneous - Age: Heterogenous (managers, supervisors, public sector employees, manual workers ; employed, unemployed and retired) - Political activity: non activist - Political orientation: Switcher voters i.e., those who have voted for RWPP in past election or would consider voting RWPP in the next election - Interpersonal relationships: participants do not know each other.
Empirical composition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No: 8 - Gender composition: Female - Socioeconomic diversity: Heterogeneous - Age: Heterogenous, ranging 21-79 - Political activity: non activist - Political orientation: Switcher voters i.e., those who have voted for RWPP in past election or would consider voting RWPP in the next election - Interpersonal relationships: participants do not know each other. - **Ethnicity**- Heterogenous including white British and British Asian – this was not specified in theoretical composition guidelines but does not appear to have adversely affected discussion.

Issues affecting the development	
Internal dynamics (e.g power dynamics, participants acquainted, etc.)	<p>None of the participants were acquainted with each other. There was a relaxed and respectful dynamic with participants listening and reacting to each other's views and feeling comfortable to disagree. Disagreements were framed as 'alternative points of view' rather than direct contentions.</p> <p>The dynamic was slightly influenced by the age gap across participants, with the youngest being 21 and the oldest 79. The oldest participant at times commented on their differing opinions as a result of belonging to an older generation.</p> <p>One participant identified their ethnicity as British Asian, however this does not appear to have affected the group dynamic and discussions around immigration were redirected by the moderator.</p> <p>Discussion around family, children, and motherhood prompted participants to share personal experiences, with one individual becoming visibly emotional. Although this moment briefly shifted focus away from discussion of problems and solutions, the moderator successfully redirected the conversation. In fact, the exchange helped unify the group around the shared challenges of motherhood.</p>
External context (e.g location of the workshop, news/political context)	<p>Location: The workshop was hosted at a hotel in Manchester City Centre. This avoided overtly framing the workshops as part of 'academic research' in comparison to hosting at a University venue.</p> <p>The workshops took place a few weeks after local elections across England in which Reform UK won the majority of council seats/councils, as well as a by-election for a parliamentary seat.</p>
Short summary of the findings	
Part I. Problem Identification	<p>Topics identified: Participants were presented with 'problem statements' in the form of quotes taken from the 2023 focus groups, each representing a key challenge that was previously identified. The quotes were shown to the participants on a card and read aloud by the moderator, who occasionally prompted discussion by highlighting the general theme to which each quote related. E.g.,</p> <p>Card 6: Increasing care responsibilities for elderly parents/state of care provision</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o <i>"As soon as our parents get older, we shove them in a home, they've got something wrong with them, I've not got enough time to look after them, they get shoved in a home."</i> <p>Participants were asked to discuss the problem statements and reflect on whether they agreed/disagreed that these reflected problems for the country as a whole. Participants often reflected on whether their personal situation related to</p>

the quote, with moderators steering discussion back to societal level.

Findings: Participants' expressed very similar attitudes to those of the 2023 focus groups. They largely agreed with the problem statements and identified that same causes/consequences of societal issues:

- 1. Balancing work and family life** – Very strong agreement that economic insecurity – and particularly the cost-of-living crisis- has meant that it is necessary for both parents in a two-parent household to work, and often to hold multiple jobs. Participants also agreed that at the same time, the cost of childcare makes it unbeneficial for both parents to work and that employment practices e.g., shift work make childcare difficult to organise around a realistic family life. While participants agreed that parents currently face challenges in balancing work and family life, they felt that this was not a 'new' phenomenon.
- 2. Loss of community; consumerism/greed** – Participants linked a perceived rise in consumerism with social media. However, there was less agreement across the group with the perception of lost community. Although it is important to note that here participants reflected heavily on their personal experiences, rather than British society as a whole.
- 3. Social media & impact on young people** – Strong agreement collectively from the group that social media is bad for children's mental health due to the promotion of problematic beauty standards and uncensored violent content. There was general agreement that social media should be policed more.
- 4. Economic insecurity & failing public services** – Participants agreed that the use of food banks is a critical problem in the UK, particularly that they are being used by those in 'well-respected' jobs like nurses and teachers. Some participants shared personal experiences of using foodbanks. The blame was placed on the cost-of-living crisis and inefficient welfare systems that are perceived not to provide effective support to working people while simultaneously being manipulated by others. Participants also felt that a cross-cutting problem with public service delivery is inefficient and expensive administration and bureaucracy, with public institutions being run 'like businesses'.
- 5. Increasing care responsibilities for elderly parents/state of care provision** – Participants expressed disagreement with the problem statement on elder care: *"As soon as our parents get older, we shove them in a home, they've got something wrong with them, I've not got enough*

	<p><i>time to look after them, they get shoved in a home”.</i> Several participants expressed challenges of caring for elderly parents at home while balancing paid work and childcare and felt there were nuanced and beneficial reasons for using private/government care. However, they also expressed a shared frustration with the quality of care provision.</p> <p>4 selected topics for solution: Participants ranked each problem statement and the first four were taken through to the next stage. The top four were:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Work/life balance 2. Economic insecurity (food banks) 3. Public services (NHS) 4. Social media & impact on children <p>Participants also considered replacing social media with adult/elder social care but decided that was more a case-by-case, rather than societal, problem.</p> <p>Topic that monopolized the discussion: Across topics, discussions continually returned to economic insecurity and the cost-of-living crisis, failing public services like the NHS and education – particularly inefficient management of services - and the pressures of raising children.</p> <p>Consensus/dissensus: There was generally strong consensus among the group in relation to the ‘problem statements’ from the previous focus groups. Where there was dissensus, it stemmed more from participant’s personal experiences. For example, there mixed agreement with the problem statement focused on loss of community, with participants reflecting on their own relationships with neighbours. A minor trend of dissensus can be observed across age, with the oldest participant (79) more regularly voicing differing opinions to the other participants, but with an awareness that this due to a generational difference.</p>
Part II. Solution Generation	<p>Suggestions of solutions and agents of chance: Participants first discussed what ‘ideal solutions/scenarios’ looked like for each of the top four topics. The aim was to keep the discussion ideational and focus on a ‘dream scenario’, however in practice, moderators found it very difficult to guide participants from thinking about practicalities, problems, and specific policies. After a brief exercise outlining ideal solutions, participants split into small groups and discuss the practical steps they would put in place to reach those outcomes. Participants were again encouraged to think outside of the box and develop creative solutions. Groups joined and fed back their thoughts and discussed agreement/disagreement.</p> <p>Findings: Ideal scenarios (participants found it difficult to talk about goals/end scenarios rather than the steps that</p>

	<p>need to be taken to address problems.)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Economic insecurity (foodbanks): Remove the need for reliance on foodbanks with higher wages and affordable housing - Work/life balance: Families have more flexibility with childcare through higher wages and greater individual financial responsibility/less materialist values. More affordable childcare; not one entire income being spent on childcare - Public services (NHS): Enough nurses to handle patients and reduce workload. No waiting lists. Higher wages for doctors and nurses. - Social media & impact on children: Children spend less time on social media and there are more outdoor communities. People are better educated on the dangers of social media. <p>Small group activity:</p> <p>Group 1: Economic insecurity (food banks)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increase wages – bring national minimum wage in line with living wage. <p>Group 2: Social media & impact on children</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increase minimum age for a social media account to 16 or 18. - Ban image filters and photo editing - Strong regulation of 18+ sexual and violent content - Social media accounts to be verified using an official ID document e.g., passport to prevent bullying or harassment - Screen time limits that cannot be overruled <p>Group 3: Work/life balance in two parent households</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Free childcare places only for working parents - to reduce pressures on nurseries – and prevent nurseries charging parents ‘supplements’ for food, nappies etc. - Greater availability of holiday clubs during school holidays and more affordable options - Set up a scheme to pay grandparents to provide childcare - Stronger education and training for young people to get better jobs to improve their financial situation <p>Group 4: Public services (NHS)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reduce the waiting list by employing more staff - Reduce the workload particularly cutting red tape and paperwork - Offer weekend and 24-hour appointments - Promote healthier lifestyles e.g., less smoking and drinking - Higher wages for doctors and nurses <p>Group discussion: The group as a whole largely agreed with all solutions suggested by each small group. When asked to reflect on the likelihood of the solutions, participants were not optimistic that as a society/nation</p>
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	<p>steps are being currently taken to address these problems. The main reasons for this that participants expressed were greed on the part of the government, political parties, and businesses like social media organisations. Particularly, participants felt ‘betrayed’ by the current Labour government. When asked if there are any groups who could take steps to deal with these issues, participants expressed support for local community and less involvement from government. No participants suggested Reform UK as an actor that could provide solutions.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Most voted items: N/A
Debriefing	N/A
Additional topics discussed	<p>The ‘solution generation’ phase ended with the moderator asking participants if they felt any ‘groups’ in the UK would be capable of enacting the solutions they had outlined. There was resounding agreement that political parties were not making any steps toward solutions. In the all-female group, participants were not informed that they all indicated an intention to vote for Reform UK and none raised Reform UK as a potential actor to provide solutions. However, participants reflection on the mainstream parties indicated a clear frustration and resentment with ‘selfish/greedy’ political elites.</p>
Preliminary conclusions	
<p>Main agreements, if any (points that the majority of the participants agreed on, important conclusions, or major discussion points, explicit if none)</p>	<p>There was strong consensus on identifying problems:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cost-of-living crisis in UK having serious detrimental impact on ordinary working families, particularly with wages not keeping in line with inflation. Food banks are seen as emblematic of a broken system - Childcare is unaffordable and not suited to the needs of many working people e.g., shift workers. Current government support (e.g. funded hours) is insufficient or inaccessible - Similarly, other public services like the NHS, welfare benefits, and education are ‘broken’. They are chronically underfunded, with too much bureaucracy leading to impersonal and inflexible services that do not meet the needs of many people’s situations. - Participants, especially parents, were concerned about the harmful impact of social media on children’s mental health, body image, and behaviour (e.g. knife crime). - Frustration across issues that ‘working people’ are being punished by selfish and out-of-touch politicians on the one hand, and selfish and ‘undeserving’ citizens e.g., immigrants, benefit cheats on the other. - There was an attempt to link issues like the NHS, housing, and welfare benefits to immigration, but

	<p>this was redirected by the moderator.</p> <p>Agreement on solutions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Higher wages would resolve problems around economic insecurity and specific problems e.g., NHS understaffing. Particularly, minimum wage should be brought in line with the living wage. - Less bureaucracy and ‘business management’ in provision of public services like healthcare, education, and childcare. This would cut costs and provide services that are more flexible to meet specific individual needs. - Stronger regulation on social media – particularly age-appropriate content. - Better funding and accessibility for childcare and healthcare in particular. Revising systems so that they meet the need of regular working people e.g., shift-workers, single-parent working households
<p>Main disagreements, if any (points that the majority of the participants disagreed on, important conclusions, or major discussion points, explicit if none)</p>	<p>There were no major points of disagreement across the group, with differences in opinion tending to reflect participant’s different personal situations rather than broader attitudes. Some areas in which different opinions were expressed:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Welfare benefits – while one participant shared personal experience of using welfare benefits and difficulties with an overly bureaucratic and underfunded system, other participants expressed resentment toward people who they felt abused the benefits system and argued there was a wider over-reliance on welfare. - On some points e.g., economic insecurity participants expressed frustration towards structural issues e.g., rental prices, but also stressed the importance of personal financial responsibility
<p>Important observations/comments</p>	<p>Moderators found it difficult to encourage participants to develop idealistic or unrealistic solutions to the problems they had identified. Instead, participants developed pragmatic solutions, often focused on cost-saving and efficiency within existing systems. There was variation across topics as participants were more ideational approaching topics like social media in comparison to established institutions like the NHS.</p>

UK Statements

Balancing work and family life

1. *“Nowadays, both parents have to work to earn the income that they need. Very few families can live off one parent’s income.”*
2. *“I think, for parents now, there’s a lot more to sort of worry about, and things, other things that they’ve got on their mind, whether it’s that they haven’t got as much time to focus on the kids”*

Loss of community (family & societal); consumerism, individualism, greed

3. *“I see whole streets and they don’t know anybody. I know everybody on that street, known them for years, but then it’ll change. Nobody knows each other so they’re not looking out for each other.”*
4. *“Material stuff doesn’t make you happy. You know, it’s good to have stuff for your kids and all that, but everything’s just consume, consume, buy, buy, buy, consume, consume, consume.”*

Support for young people (school pressures, lack of opportunities, social media)

5. *“It’s not normal. It’s not normal, and social media is just...is just warping the kids’ minds.... It’s destroying kids’ self-esteem, everything.”*

Increasing care responsibilities for elderly parents/state of care provision

6. *“As soon as our parents get older, we shove them in a home, they’ve got something wrong with them, I’ve not got enough time to look after them, they get shoved in a home.”*

Economic insecurity (impact on family/community)

7. *“We get people coming to the food bank – we do get nurses, we get like these people that’s working around the clock and they still come to the food bank.”*

Failing public services (police, NHS, schools, councils)

8. *“The NHS has got a lot worse. You can’t even get a doctor’s appointment these days. That’s a struggle. Waiting lists.”*

vii. Workshops Description for Ethics Committee Clearance

Overview

Human beings are inherently diverse, with individuals expressing a broad range of needs, concerns, and priorities influenced by factors such as gender, social class, ethnicity, and age. Effectively addressing this diversity is essential for fostering inclusive and representative societal frameworks and policy. The EU-funded UNTWIST project seeks to explore how public narratives resonate with citizens and to collaboratively develop strategies that ensure a better understanding and political representation of their diverse needs.

A key component are the the co-creation workshops, which will bring together participants from varied backgrounds to identify and discuss their priorities and concerns. These workshops emphasize participatory research, empowering citizens to contribute directly to the development of evidence-based recommendations. The workshops build upon the focus groups conducted in 2023 (insert reference to ethics committee approval). By facilitating inclusive discussions, the project aims to capture a wide range of perspectives and create practical tools to inform policy and decision-making. The insights gained from these workshops will be compiled into a handbook designed to guide organizations and policymakers in addressing the diverse needs of society. By prioritizing inclusivity and collaboration, the UNTWIST project seeks to foster a deeper understanding of societal dynamics and promote solutions that reflect and respect the diversity of citizens' experiences.

Organization

The workshops will be organized and conducted by the national teams in Spain, Germany, Switzerland, Denmark, and Hungary. The activities are scheduled to take place in May 2025. Each workshop will be carried out by the respective local team in the local language to ensure accessibility and effective communication. Each national team will conduct two workshops. Each workshop will last approximately two hours. Each group will aim for 6–8 participants. Recruitment efforts will be designed to secure approximately 20 participants per country in total, allowing for potential last-minute dropouts based on prior focus group experiences. Each session will be facilitated by up to two experienced moderators.

The format of the workshops—online or in-person—will be determined by each national team based on their logistical capacities and the specific local context. For online workshops, teams will utilize video-conferencing software (e.g., Zoom) and interactive tools (e.g., Miro, Padlet) to facilitate collaboration and engagement. For in-person workshops, teams will utilize analog interactive tools, such as sticky notes and whiteboards. The reasoning for choosing the location of in-person workshops can be similar to that of the focus groups.

Participants profiles and recruitment

Participants for the workshops will be recruited by an external third party, either the survey administrators (Verian) or recruitment agencies previously engaged for the focus group. This institution will take care of the screening process, ensuring that participants in the workshops the following criteria:

- **Gender Composition:** Workshops will either consist of mixed gender groups or same-sex groups, following the approach used by each respective country team during the focus group phase.

- **Socioeconomic Diversity:** Efforts will be made to form groups that are as socioeconomically diverse as possible. Partners can choose to select more homogeneous groups depending on local context, research questions and experience from the focus group.
- **Age Groups:** efforts will be made to have groups that have a similar age bracket as the one used in the focus groups.
- **Political Activity:** Participants shall not be politically active or affiliated with activist groups.
- **Political Orientation:** Groups will include a mix of political orientations, with ideally at least one or two participants who sympathize with right-wing populist parties, alongside one switcher voters, one moderate centrists, and potentially other party voters based on local contexts and requirements. The final composition of participants in the workshops will be set up by each local team based on previous workshop experience and relevance for the analysis of the workshop discussions.
- **Interpersonal Relationships:** Participants will be selected to ensure they do not know each other personally, fostering open and unbiased discussions.

This recruitment strategy is designed to create dynamic and representative groups that reflect diverse perspectives, enabling the workshops to achieve meaningful and comprehensive insights. Partners should adapt these criteria in the document they submit to their local ethics committee based on scientific needs and feasibility. They can decide to have more homogeneous groups on criteria they expect to be most sensitive (e.g. same-gender group if gender is expected to be the most conflictive aspect or the main scientific angle).

Data collection and processing

Recruitment will be handled by recruitment agencies contracted by each national team. These recruitment agencies will screen participants based on the above-mentioned participants profiles, select, contact, and arrange the venue of the participants. The local teams do not gather any personal information about the participants.

Prior to the beginning of the workshop, participants receive an information sheet and sign an informed consent form, either in person or digitally, depending on the workshop setting. For this, an information sheet and the consent form from the focus groups will be used and modified accordingly by each national team.

The workshops will be recorded, and pictures from the mindmaps will be saved. The recruitment agency will transcribe and anonymize the recordings, erasing names and any other personal detail that may lead to personal identification or the identification of other persons, places, addresses, etc., that are mentioned during the workshop. Video recordings will be destroyed after transcriptions are finalized. Audio recordings will be kept until the end of the project and then destroyed

The data will be analyzed for academic purposes by the UNTWIST research team, and the results will serve to infer policy recommendations that the team will share with interested political actors. Results will also be published and disseminated in academic formats.

Workshop Structure

The starting points for the workshops are the results from the focus group which were previously conducted in 2023. Data collected during the focus groups helped identify areas in which citizens felt “maltreated”, “forgotten”, or “undermined” by mainstream parties and which, at the same time, are approached by right wing populist parties in anti-gender/equality way, such as **health, family, education, economy, civil rights, security policies, gender norms, material inequality**. Participants will be encouraged to propose solutions to the problems they identify with, fostering a bottom-up and co-creative

approach that allows them to influence political discourse directly. Two professionals will facilitate the workshops and ensure an open and inclusive atmosphere. The workshop will be divided into four parts:

1. Introduction (~15 minutes)

Participants will engage in an icebreaker activity to get acquainted with one another and guidelines for interaction will be established to ensure a respectful and collaborative environment, allowing space for participants to ask questions.

2. Problem identification (~45 minutes)

Participants are presented with statements from the focus groups. Topics from these statements include: living conditions of individuals and families ; economy and employment ; education ; support for vulnerable people ; relations between parents and children ; elderly people ; care works ; relations between men and women ; participation of women in the labor market). These statements are printed on paper cards or written on digital sticky-notes. Possible statements could be "because I'm working full time I cannot properly take care of my family" OR persona style "Lilly is a 40 years old woman living with her husband and her 2 kids. She works full time as a nurse. Her biggest concern is that she feels she cannot properly take care of her family". Participants are given the time to read through the cards, and invited to select those they identify with, discuss and modify these statements based on the issues they are facing. Participants are invited to explore other topics, but facilitators must ensure they remain in scope of the workshop. Finally, participants may use dot-voting to select some statements they decide to focus on.

3. Solution generation (~60 minutes)

Participants are presented with statements from the policy recommendations already produced, invited to modify them and to come up with new statements/ideas that address these issues and help mitigate them. First, they can suggest as many different options as they want. They begin by doing this individually (~5 minutes), on sticky notes, then, they discuss with the group the possible options. Participants are invited to create together as many solutions as they like, both realistic and nonrealistic. At the end, each participant gets to put a dot vote on the suggestions they find most desirability (~10 minutes). Participants are then invited to share their reasoning behind the choices.

4. Wrap up (~10 minutes)

Collect feedback from each participant on their experience of the workshops, and answer potential questions (to expect: anonymity in the transcription, confidentiality, and outcomes of the workshops). Participants are asked to fill in a form (anonymous, no name or address required) for profiling. They may choose the pseudonym they want us to refer them to in the transcriptions (in order

to identify the profile). The information to be compiled includes gender, age, education level, professional status, social class, household and personal income, ideology and voting recall.

Facilitation guidelines

The workshop will be presented as a discussion on people's issues and needs in their daily lives in the specific country, avoiding project jargon.

During the workshop, facilitators should:

- intervene to redirect the group to the main topic if it wanders too far away.
- use previous participants' framing and verbatims to refocus or revitalize the discussion.
- orient towards real life experiences and problems and avoid general discourse.
- pay attention to signs of distress by participants and try to reconduct and reduce the stress of the situation if necessary. Intervene to cut any verbal aggression or disrespect between participants before it escalates.

- encourage participants to respectfully voice their opinions even though it differs from other participants.
- avoid mentioning partisan labels (e.g., "right," "center," "far/extreme"), and instead focus on practical, day-to-day challenges that participants face (e.g. childcare, family life, welfare state, labor market, gender roles, material inequality, violence)
- not bring "sex", "gender" or "feminism" explicitly into the discussion unless it is mentioned by the group
- Some sexist, xenophobic or racist comments are likely to happen. Do not rebuke them. Do not give explicit or implicit approval either. Let the conversation follow if the attack is not personally directed among participants. .
- rules of interaction: participants should be mindful of other participants, do not need to ask for word turns, but should not talk on top of each other

Expected outcomes

The workshops should gather participants' views of gender-based needs and ideas on how to address issues they are facing. Not only will the workshops provide important data to build policy recommendations, but also the organization of the workshop itself can serve as a policy recommendation on how to include citizens in policy making.

viii. Ethical clearance Spain

Vicerrectorado de Investigación, Transferencia y Doctorado

**D^a. ANTONIA MERCEDES JIMÉNEZ RODRÍGUEZ,
VICERRECTORA DE INVESTIGACIÓN, TRANSFERENCIA Y DOCTORADO
DE LA UNIVERSIDAD PABLO DE OLAVIDE,**

Autoriza con **código 24/11-54**, la propuesta de investigación realizada por **D. Antonia María Ruiz Jiménez**, relativa al proyecto/procedimiento denominado **"(WP9: Co-develop policy recommendations with citizens and stakeholders): Soluciones ciudadanas: colaborando por un futuro mejor (taller de ciencia ciudadana)"**, ya que respeta los principios fundamentales de la Declaración de Helsinki, del convenio del Consejo de Europa relativo a los Derechos Humanos y la Biomedicina, de la Declaración Universal de la UNESCO sobre el genoma humano y los Derechos Humanos, del convenio para la protección de los Derechos Humanos y la dignidad del ser humano con respecto a las aplicaciones de la biología y la medicina (Convenio de Oviedo relativo a los Derechos Humanos y la Biomedicina), así como la ley de protección de datos española (Ley Orgánica 3/2018, de 5 de diciembre).

Y para que así conste a los efectos oportunos, firmo la presente en Sevilla a la fecha de la firma electrónica.

Antonia Mercedes Jiménez Rodríguez
Vicerrectora de Investigación, Transferencia y Doctorado
Presidenta de la Comisión Ética para Investigación con seres Humanos (CEIH)

Código Seguro De Verificación	MwLXmoFJbvB1IbOVP20gOw==	Fecha	20/12/2024	
Normativa	Este informe tiene carácter de copia electrónica auténtica con validez y eficacia administrativa de ORIGINAL (art. 27 Ley 39/2015).			
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ix. Ethical clearance Switzerland

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**UNIVERSITÄT
BERN**

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University of Bern
Institute of Sociology
Fabrikstrasse 8
3012 Bern
Switzerland

Wirtschafts- und
Sozialwissenschaftliche Fakultät
Ethikkommission

Bern, March 19, 2025

Decision on the ethical standard of research project «UNTWIST: policy recommendations to regain "losers of feminism" as mainstream voters» By Prof. Dr. Michèle Amacker

The Ethics Committee of the Faculty of Business, Economics and Social Sciences of the University of Bern declares that the research project «UNTWIST: policy recommendations to regain "losers of feminism" as mainstream voters» complies with the ethical standards of the faculty. Ethical clearance was provided March 19, 2025. The project has the serial number 142025.

Prof. Dr. Axel Franzen
Head of the ethics committee

x. Ethical clearance Hungary

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Zsuzsanna ÁRENDÁS
Deputy
Institutional Ethics Review Board

1-FOIG/6-2/2025

Budapest, 14 January 2025

Decision

Subject: Ethical Research Review – Katalin Tardos – UNTWIST – "citizen workshops"

The Board has reviewed the information you submitted.

The submitted documents have convincingly shown that the research is compliant with the research ethics principles of the HUN-REN Centre for Social Sciences.

It is the responsibility of the Researcher, as the project is proceeding, to update the research documentation shared with the Research Documentation Centre and the Research Ethics Committee; with particular attention to the information sheet and consent form prepared for workshop participants.

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Zsuzsanna Árendás'.

Zsuzsanna ÁRENDÁS

IRB / Centre for Social Sciences

xi. Ethical clearance Germany

Universität des Saarlandes
Philosophische Fakultät
Empirische Humanwissenschaften

Bearbeitungsnummer
(von der Kommission
auszufüllen)

Ethikkommission

ANTRAGSFORMULAR

Einzelantrag

Gruppenantrag

Veränderungsantrag (Genehmigungs-Nummer:)

(Im Falle eines Veränderungsantrags sind bei den Punkten 2-6 nur die Veränderungen aufzuführen)

1. Allgemeine Angaben

a. Name und Kontaktinformation der antragsstellenden Person	Giuseppe Carteny: giuseppe.carteny@uni-saarland.de
b. Name(n) der durchführenden Person(en), einschliesslich Kontaktinformationen	
c. Wer finanziert das Vorhaben (Forschungsträger)?	Horizon Europe
d. Thema/Titel des Vorhabens	1. UNTWIST
e. Zusammenfassung des Vorhabens (max. 1000 Zeichen)	<p>UNTWIST: Human beings are inherently diverse, with individuals expressing a broad range of needs, concerns, and priorities influenced by factors such as gender, social class, ethnicity, and age. Effectively addressing this diversity is essential for fostering inclusive and representative societal frameworks and policy. The EU-funded UNTWIST project seeks to explore how public narratives resonate with citizens and to collaboratively develop strategies that ensure a better understanding and political representation of their diverse needs.</p> <p>A key component is the co-creation workshops, which will bring together participants from varied backgrounds to identify and discuss their priorities and concerns. These workshops emphasize participatory research, empowering citizens to contribute directly to the development of evidence-based recommendations. The workshops build upon the focus groups conducted in 2023 (insert reference to ethics committee approval). The insights gained from these workshops will be compiled into a handbook designed to guide organizations and policymakers in addressing the diverse needs of society.</p>
f. Verlangt der Forschungsträger eine Begutachtung des Vorhabens durch eine Ethikkommission?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Ja <input type="checkbox"/> Nein
g. Hat der/die Datenschutzbeauftragte dem Antrag bereits zugestimmt?	<input type="checkbox"/> Ja (dann kann 5. übersprungen werden) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Nein

1

2. Verfahren des Vorhabens

<p>a. Teilnehmende (Angestrebte Anzahl, Geschlecht, Alter, Ausbildung, Gruppenzugehörigkeit)</p> <p>Maximum 16 participants, evenly split in two workshops.</p>
<p>b. Welche Personendaten werden erhoben (Studienvariablen)?</p> <p>Anonymised transcriptions of the workshop discussion. The workshops will be recorded. The recruitment agency will transcribe and anonymize the recordings, erasing names and any other personal detail that may lead to personal identification or the identification of other persons, places, addresses, etc., that are mentioned during the workshop. Video recordings will be destroyed after transcriptions are finalized. Audio recordings will be kept until the end of the project and then destroyed. The information will be analysed for academic purposes by the UNTWIST research team, the results will be published and disseminated only in an aggregated manner, and the results will serve to infer policy recommendations that the team will share with interested political actors. Results will also be published and disseminated in academic formats.</p>
<p>c. Wie ist die Durchführung der Studie aus der Sicht der Teilnehmenden gestaltet? Ggf. in separatem Dokument darstellen und dem Antrag beifügen.</p> <p>The starting points for the workshops are the results from the focus group which were previously conducted in 2023. Data collected during the focus groups helped identify areas in which citizens felt "maltreated", "forgotten", or "undermined" by mainstream parties and which, at the same time, are approached by right wing populist parties in anti-gender/equality way, such as health, family, education, economy, civil rights, security policies, gender norms, material inequality. Participants will be encouraged to propose solutions to the problems they identify with, fostering a bottom-up and co-creative approach that allows them to influence political discourse directly. Two professionals will facilitate the workshops and ensure an open and inclusive atmosphere. The workshop will be divided into four parts:</p> <p>1. Introduction (~15 minutes) Participants will engage in an icebreaker activity to get acquainted with one another and guidelines for interaction will be established to ensure a respectful and collaborative environment, allowing space for participants to ask questions.</p> <p>2. Problem identification (~45 minutes) Participants are presented with statements from the focus groups. Topics from these statements include: living conditions of individuals and families; economy and employment; education; support for vulnerable people; relations between parents and children; elderly people; care works; relations between men and women; participation of women in the labor market. These statements are printed on paper cards or written on digital sticky-notes. Possible statements could be "because I'm working full time I cannot properly take care of my family" or persona style "Lilly is a 40 years old woman living with her husband and her 2 kids. She works full time as a nurse. Her biggest concern is that she feels she cannot properly take care of her family". Participants are given the time to read through the cards, and invited to select those they identify with, discuss and modify these statements based on the issues they are facing. Participants are invited to explore other topics, but facilitators must ensure they remain in scope of the workshop. Finally, participants may use dot-voting to select some statements they decide to focus on.</p> <p>3. Solution generation (~60 minutes) Participants are presented with statements from the policy recommendations already produced, invited to modify them and to come up with new statements/ideas that address these issues and help mitigate them. First, they can suggest as many different options as they want. They begin by doing this individually (~5 minutes), on sticky notes, then, they discuss with the group the possible options. Participants are invited to create together as many solutions as they like, both realistic and non-realistic. At the end, each participant gets to put a dot vote on the suggestions they find most desirability (~10 minutes). Participants are then invited to share their reasoning behind the choices.</p> <p>4. Wrap up (~10 minutes) Collect feedback from each participant on their experience of the workshops, and answer potential questions (to expect: anonymity in the transcription, confidentiality, and outcomes of the</p>

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workshops). Participants are asked to fill in a form (anonymous, no name or address required) for profiling. They may choose the pseudonym they want us to refer them to in the transcriptions (in order to identify the profile). The information to be compiled includes gender, age, education level, professional status, social class, household and personal income, ideology and voting recall.

3. Spezifische ethische Aspekte des Vorhabens

a. Wird die Teilnahme an dem Vorhaben den Probanden vergütet oder bekommen sie eine Aufwandsentschädigung? <i>Wenn ja, was, wie viel?</i>
The participants will be reimbursed for the travel expenses, with a maximum limit of 50 euros.
b. Wird über Ziele und Verfahren vor der Studie aufgeklärt (einschließlich Dauer der Untersuchung, Belastungen und Risiken durch spezifische Untersuchungsverfahren, über Vergütungen und andere Zusagen und über die jederzeitige und folgenlose Rücktrittsmöglichkeit von der Teilnahme-Bereitschaft)? <i>Wenn nein, warum? Ggf. vollständiges Informationsmaterial dem Antrag beifügen.</i>
Yes. Prior to the beginning of the workshop, participants will receive an information sheet and sign an informed consent form depending on the workshop setting.
c. Ist die Freiwilligkeit der Teilnahme aufgrund einer informierten Einverständniserklärung gewährleistet?
Yes
d. Können möglichen Teilnehmenden durch Nicht-Teilnahme Nachteile entstehen? Wenn ja, welche?
No.
e. Können Teilnehmende auch während des Vorhabens jederzeit ohne Angaben von Gründen und ohne Nachteile ihre Teilnahme zurückziehen?
Yes.
f. Bei Teilnehmenden unter 16 Jahren: Wird das schriftliche Einverständnis des gesetzlichen Vertreters eingeholt?
N/A Participants are all aged 18 or over.
g. Ist die Teilnahme von eingeschränkt urteilsfähigen, urteilsunfähigen oder unmündigen Personen möglich oder vorgesehen? <i>Wenn ja, bitte erläutern:</i>
No.
h. Setzen sich die Teilnehmenden einem Risiko aus, welches mit einer Versicherung abgedeckt werden muss? Wenn ja, welches Risiko besteht und welche Versicherung wurde abgeschlossen? Bitte ggf. Versicherungsunterlagen beifügen.
No
i. Wie werden die Teilnehmenden nach Beendigung des Vorhabens informiert? Was wird wie rückgemeldet? <i>Ggf in separatem Dokument beifügen.</i>
The debriefing step of the focus group will include a brief summary of the project for participants. At this stage, participants will receive reassurance that all collected data will be anonymised and analysed as an aggregate.

4. Belastungen während der Untersuchung

a. Wird die <i>physische Integrität</i> der Teilnehmenden tangiert (z.B. durch Einnahme von Arzneimitteln, Entnahme von Blut)? Können negative Folgen entstehen (z.B. Kopfschmerzen)? <i>Wenn ja, bitte erläutern.</i>
No

<p>b. Wird die <i>psychische Integrität</i> der Teilnehmenden tangiert (z.B. Konzentrationsfähigkeit, Induktion von negativen Emotionen)? Können negative psychische Folgen eintreten? <i>Wenn ja, bitte erläutern.</i></p> <p>No.</p>
<p>c. Wird durch die Teilnahme die <i>soziale Integrität</i> tangiert (z.B. die Teilnahme trägt zu einem schlechten Ruf bei). Können negative soziale Folgen entstehen? <i>Wenn ja, bitte erläutern.</i></p> <p>No.</p>
<p>d. Wenn Sie bei einer der Fragen 4a-c mit „ja“ geantwortet haben, gehen die Belastungen oder Folgen über das alltägliche Mass hinaus („minimal risk“)?</p> <p>N/A</p>
<p>e. Wenn Sie bei Frage 4d mit „ja“ geantwortet haben, geben Sie bitte eine Begründung für Ihr Vorgehen an und erläutern Sie die Schutzmassnahmen, die Sie für die Teilnehmenden treffen werden:</p> <p>N/A</p>
<p>h. Werden die Teilnehmenden gebeten, persönliche Erfahrungen (z.B. belastende Erlebnisse), sensitive Informationen (z.B. sexuelles Verhalten, Drogenkonsum) oder Einstellungen (z.B. politische Präferenzen) preiszugeben? <i>Wenn ja, bitte erläutern.</i></p> <p>Participants will be asked to provide preferences, new statements, and ideas about policy recommendations for addressing the following issues: living conditions of individuals and families; economy and employment; education; support for vulnerable people; relations between parents and children; elderly people; care works; relations between men and women; participation of women in the labor market.</p>
<p>i. Werden die Teilnehmenden absichtlich unvollständig oder falsch (mit dem Ziel der Täuschung) über die Ziele und das Verfahren des Vorhabens informiert (z.B. durch anipulierte Rückmeldungen über ihre Leistungen)? <i>Wenn ja, bitte erläutern (insbesondere das „Debriefing“).</i></p> <p>No.</p>
<p>h. Wird es notwendig sein, dass Personen an der Studie teilnehmen, ohne dies zu wissen und ohne informierte Einwilligung gegeben zu haben? (z. B. verdeckte Beobachtung von Personen an nicht-öffentlichen Orten)</p> <p>No.</p>

5. Angaben zum Datenschutz

<p>a. Sind Bild-, Film- oder Tonaufnahmen oder andere Verhaltensregistrierungen vorgesehen? Yes, sound recordings.</p>
<p>b. Werden die erhobenen Daten anonymisiert? <i>Wenn nein, warum nicht?</i></p> <p>Yes</p>
<p>c. Wie wird die Vertraulichkeit der Daten gewährleistet?</p> <p>We produce anonymised transcripts, wherein all participants are identified only by a number or by pseudonym provided by the participants.</p>
<p>d. Werden erhobene Daten nach Ablauf einer bestimmten Zeit teilweise oder ganz gelöscht?</p> <p>No. The anonymised data will be stored using the USAAR system hizCloud for the duration of the project (until March 2026) and then shared publicly via Zenodo, a European Commission co-founded repository for publications and data, in accordance with the open data requirements of the Horizon Europe program.</p>

6. Sonstige Angaben

a. Sonstige Angaben, die für die Ethikkommission relevant sein könnten:

Datum und Unterschrift der Antrag stellenden Person

07.01.2025

xii. Ethical clearance Denmark

ROSKILDE UNIVERSITY
The Research Ethics Committee

Att: Laura Horn
Department of Social Sciences and Business
Roskilde University

DATE
09.04.2025

OUR REFERENCE
2025-8

YOUR REFERENCE
emde

Research ethics approval of the research project "EU Horizon UNTWIST, workshops WP9"

The Research Ethics Committee at Roskilde University hereby approves the application for research ethics approval of the research project "*EU Horizon UNTWIST, workshops WP9*", as submitted by Laura Horn in the application dated 09.04.2025.

For this approval, the submitted application is attached.

On behalf of the Research Ethics Committee,

Emil Emde Jensen
Research Consultant, RUC Research Office
Secretary for The Research Ethics Committee

Roskilde University
Administration

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Roskilde Universitet CVR-nr.: 29 05 75 59

xiii. Ethical clearance UK

Partners at the University of Manchester have filled out the University of Manchester's Ethics Decision Tool which informed them that they did not need ethical approval (see attached screenshot). The workshops come under "standard market research" which does not require them to go through the University's ethical procedures, as confirmed by the Ethics Decision Tool. They will only receive the anonymised data from the company they are using, which is a member of the Market Research Society (<https://www.mrs.org.uk/>) and follows their guidance. They will not be present at the workshops or have any interaction with the workshop participants.

